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**Perceived service quality and satisfaction impact on student
loyalty in higher education institutions**

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INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions are becoming increasingly businesslike and that leads to take student loyalty into important consideration and strategic subject for universities and colleges. (Helgesen & Nettet, 2009). The number of that kind institutions are rapidly growing, thus it results in higher competition and noticeable decline of enrolled students. In such marketplace, it is very important to find the proper ways how to attract and retain students with sufficient academic performance and at the same time to be able to accomplish desirable benchmark of student enrollment as it leads to run higher education institutions operations properly. In other words, it is assumed that for any academic service it is crucial to discover and measure how different aspects and areas contribute to student loyalty in order to enhance both repurchase of the service and spread of positive word-of-mouth or recommendations. Moreover, consistent monitoring and development of the key contributing factors in loyalty improve general image and increase profits of the organization. (Helgesen, 2007; Austin, 2017). In addition to that, sustainable and profitable relationship between customers (students) and the service provider in today's competitive and global market is one of the most challenging areas (Chuah, 2017).

Furthermore, according to Chen (2016), it is assumed that due to costs escalating and the decline of resources, higher education institutions should try to strength their overall community support and to serve not only the educational needs of students, but also the high satisfaction among the service. Correspondingly, as Pham and Lai (2016) state in their study, tuition fees are meaningful source of income for higher education institutions, especially for some developed countries where international higher education and attraction of self-funding foreign students has become an effective export industry. Thus, it could be considered that better identification and deeper understanding of student loyal behaviour in educational service is important from many aspects.

Even though, previous studies paid increased attention on analysing student loyalty antecedents such as satisfaction, service quality, university image or other non-academic aspect, the more detailed of those significant variables and other elements which may have direct or moderating impact on service loyalty has not fully been explored (Annamdevula & Bellamkonda, 2014). Moreover, by that perspective, interaction effect of such variables as a field of studies, level of education, course or attendance of lectures on various elements in student's

perceived educational service quality, satisfaction and loyalty have not received much attention. Thus, this paper will try to explore this gap in more details.

Research problem. As it was mentioned previously, there are several essential factors which mainly contribute to making student loyalty an important issue for institutions offering higher education, such as new legislation designed to reform higher education, changes in future funding (more performance-based public funding regarding the level of employment or other indicators), increased student mobility, global competition, demographic changes and increased emigration that resulted in a decline in the number of potential students (Nesset and Helgesen, 2009). Therefore, the main problem of this research is to investigate the following questions: What is the general relationship between student different elements of perceived educational service quality, satisfaction and student loyalty intentions; Do different field of study, level of education, course or attendance of lectures have different impact on student's perceived educational service quality aspects, satisfaction and loyalty intentions? The study will be conducted by gathering relevant data from the university database and its semi-annual questionnaires.

The purpose of this research is: to evaluate above described factors and elements impact on the loyalty in higher education institutions. Therefore, the main objectives that will be examined in this research paper are the following:

1. To determine the impact of different field of study, level of education, course or attendance of lectures on the elements of perceived service quality and overall satisfaction on student loyalty.
2. To determine and describe the impact of elements of perceived service quality and overall satisfaction on student loyalty.
3. To demonstrate an understanding of the relation between different aspects of student perceived educational service quality, satisfaction and loyalty.
4. To develop a model presenting how different aspects of student perceived educational service quality and satisfaction can influence or vary between different field of studies, level of education, study course or lectures attendance towards student loyalty intentions on their academic institution.

5. To extract, collect and analyse relevant student data from universities specific databases regarding factors that student loyalty in higher education service.

6. To make conclusions and suggestion for the thesis.

In chapter 1 the literature analysis of loyalty, satisfaction and perceived service quality is presented. Subsequently, further theoretical framework around other variables that can influence loyalty in service is presented. Thirdly, deeper insights about specific variables that can impact loyalty intentions in higher education service are provided. In chapter 2, proposed research model, hypothesis, data collection methods and instruments will be presented and discussed. In chapter 3, collected data is analysed and discussed. Finally, the main conclusions and suggestions regarding the literature review, methodological part and practice have been proposed upon finding of the research paper.

Study limitations and problems:

Although, collected survey panel provides relevant data regarding students loyalty intentions (the questionnaire consisting of 55105 respondents (students from different faculty's, study programmes, courses or degree) where one of the survey question identifying student loyalty intention - 'willingness to recommend chosen study programme to your friend or fellow' or 'If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university' was conducted), various aspects of perceived educational service quality and overall satisfaction, the database of university semi-annual questionnaires did not provide students demographic data. Moreover, the investigation in this paper was limited only by the information that was lawfully provided. Student surveys were covered only by the period from 2014 to 2016 academic year.

1. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW OF LOYALTY, PERCEIVED SERVICE QUALITY AND SATISFACTION

1.1. Customer loyalty concept and differences of its perception

The concept of loyalty has been perceived in the various ways and identified having different approaches by previous researchers in the existing literature. According to Bardauskaite (2014), until dates back to yearly 1970s loyalty has been conceptualized and described mainly as only behavioural component that corresponds to customer which makes a repurchase of product or service towards the same brand or provider. Notwithstanding, major changes in a marketing field paradigms that suggested higher orientation to the customer, its needs, satisfaction, successful long-term relationship with organization has lead to adopt insights into loyalty approaches based on other important aspects than actual repeat purchase behaviour in further researches (Day, 1969). Correspondingly, since then, scholars have found that customer psychological-attitudinal involvements such as positive reviews, preference for particular brand over other existing alternatives and competitors or intention to recommend product or service contributes to a strong customer-brand (organization) relationship as well as repeat purchases and should be taken into important consideration while reflecting loyalty concept (Matony et al. 2000, Lam et al. 2004, Cahill et al. 2007). The authors suggested to define customer loyalty as two dimensional construct – attitudinal and behavioural, but with some distinctions. While Lam (2004) has seen loyalty indicators as recommending a service provider to other customers (attitudinal component) and repeatedly patronizing the provider (behavioural component), Cahill et al. (2007) extended recommendations with positive reviews, but enrolled those two indicators to ,in contrast, behavioural category. These findings regarding the importance of including both attitudinal and behavioural refers to the fact that taking into account only the increased purchases and income as a loyalty measurement basis, organizations often can have discrepancies due to random aspect when purchasing is made only because of limited availability of product or service at the purchasing moment, as well as the current consumer's financial status or some problematic situations related with customer.

Nevertheless, despite the above described framework wide acceptance and support by numerous researches, some scholars, for example, Yam&Kannan (1999) criticizing the effectiveness of attitudinal dimension as a loyalty observation, perhaps, due to the fact that even very high positive attitude and strong emotional commitments could never transfer into actual purchase, thus it could be a problematic way to predict customer future behaviour. Consequently, it can be assumed that the most appropriate indicator of loyalty is “the past purchase behaviour combined with recommendation intentions or behaviour“ (Bardauskaite, 2014).

1.2. Variety of the antecedents of loyalty

Kuusik (2007) indicated that there are a number of factors which can have an impact on customer loyalty. Those factors could be related with various areas such as business process, customer or environmental issues. In addition, it was assumed that the influence of those factors is also dependent on the level of loyalty of customers. In other words, the level is perceived as a reason why customers are loyal – “if they are forced to be loyal; loyal due to inertia or functionally loyal”. For instance, if the customer is functionally loyal (which could mean that the preferable product or service creates high quality or price-based value) then the above mentioned factors may have different impact on customer loyalty compared to one’s with forced loyalty (when the customer is loyal due to exit barriers). The following paragraphs will discuss in more details factors that are mainly discussed by various authors as having an influence in customer loyalty intentions.

From a customer perspective, there are a lot of essential business performance indicators such as service quality and value, satisfaction, trust, organization image or reputation that cover management, operational and supporting activities in a company. When translating this into education institutions context, the similar indicators could be applied (Helgesen and Hessel, 2007 ; Mohamad and Awang, 2009 ; Mendez et al. 2009). All those factors may have influence on student loyalty. However, a variety of factors appear to differ in authors researches. For example, while Helgesen and Nessel (2009) stated that such factors as student satisfaction, and service quality are the most important factors leading loyalty, other scholars Brown and Mazzarol (2009) recognized that it is worth to include university image and reputation into

loyalty framework as those factors showed also some impact on students value perception. Moreover, such researchers as Aritonang (2014) emphasized the importance of not only satisfaction, but also of trust and social identification claiming that the results of the study confirm social identification and trust positive, significant link to loyalty. Correspondingly, our study will explore one of the mostly mentioned, but having not unified view towards its influence, factor in the prior studies – satisfaction (Schlesinger et al., 2016)

Satisfaction. Satisfaction has been perceived as a central concept in the existing marketing literature. However, despite the broad popularity among empirical studies in academic literature, the concept of satisfaction is perceived from different sides and interpretations by various authors. The authors mainly relate the concept with emotional, affective or evaluative aspects. For example, while some authors as Llach et al. (2015) perceive satisfaction as the comparative evaluation between the customer primary expectations and the actual experience received by the usage of product or service, another scholar Karbasi et al. (2014) define satisfaction as overall psychological state based on the evaluation of the experience and relationship between the customer and company. Moreover, it is assumed that usually the perception of service quality/value is the main driver of satisfaction, thus the more difficult is to evaluate perceived quality, the more higher impact have the customer prior expectations Yi (1993).

In the existing literature, there have been conducted numerous studies towards the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty from different perspectives and points of view. Broadly speaking, as Bove and Johnson (2006) claim, in a marketing field the **general linkage** between those two variables is perceived as positively correlated. Nevertheless, as Apostle loyalty model (developed by Harvard Business School (Figure 1)) suggests, higher level of customer satisfaction do not ensure higher customer intention or actual behaviour to re-buy the same product or service. Thus, according to this model, customers behaviour among satisfaction-loyalty linkage could not be described uniquely. Contrariwise, they may be classified into more different categories such as defectors, hostages, mercenaries and loyalist. To be more precise, loyalists are perceived as those customers who are satisfied and express it by spreading positive word-of-mouth and repeat purchases; mercenaries are defined as satisfied but not loyal customers who are price sensitive and quite easily switching to another brand/supplier; hostages – not satisfied customers, but make repeat purchases due to high switching barriers/costs or lack

of alternatives/ other competitors. Finally, defectors could be interpreted as both dissatisfied and not loyal customers who tend to communicate negative word-of-mouth.

Figure 1: The loyalty- satisfaction link (Apostle model)

Source : Harvard Business School

The model explains that loyalists and hostages (even with the low level of satisfaction) are the highest-profit customer groups due to their the most likely repurchasing behaviour (actual loyalty) towards the same provider or supplier(Lee et al. 2001). The loyalty behaviour among the low satisfied customers (hostages) could be possibly related with the lack of alternatives or high switching costs.

In addition to that, some researchers as Tuu and Olsen (2016) in their recent study suggest to divide various approaches of satisfaction-loyalty relation into three categories claiming that it could help better understand different results and outcomes in various investigations among this linkage. Those categories are: satisfaction – new drivers approach, mediator-moderator approach and linear-nonlinear approach. Broadening those approaches and giving more clear explanations,

'satisfaction-new drivers' approach suggests that in order to understand satisfaction influence on loyalty the antecedents of both satisfaction and loyalty should be clearly discussed and taken into account. In other words, it is believed that in different situations and industries, various set of antecedents explain customer loyalty behaviour, thus the level of satisfaction also plays not an identical roles. Correspondingly, by that perspective, other authors such as Bardauskaite (2014) also support this view and suggest to analyze the influence of satisfaction with **goods** and **services** on loyalty separately. It is explained by important differences in basic characteristics among items and activities such as intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability and perishability. To give more broad explanation, intangibility is perceived as the service characteristic which refers that it is not made by physical substance, thus it cannot be seen or touched. Heterogeneity is defined also as service characteristic referring its disparateness (services cannot be standardized due to its customer-based adaptation of service performance). The third different service characteristic compared to goods –inseparability- refers that the consumption and production of the service occurs at the same time. Finally, the last mentioned service characteristic by scholar Bardauskaite (2014) is perishability, which refers to the fact that service cannot be produced and stockpiled before the consumption compared to the goods. All those characteristics are the reason why some authors are tend to distinct customers satisfaction and ,consequently, loyalty on service and goods.

For instance, higher perceived risk is assigned to service than goods due to intangibility. Accordingly, Chiu et al. (2014) pointed out that perceived risk has not very strong, but still significant negative influence on even experienced customer intention to make a repeat purchase, thus it may be assumed that satisfaction could play a weaker role in loyalty on service compared to goods. Moreover, some authors define the concept of satisfaction as comparison between primary expectation and the actual performance of the product. Thus, it could be considered that due to intangibility, the level of satisfaction might be lower on service than on goods and, consequently, it can cause lower intentions to be loyal. In addition, from customer perspective greater durability among some services than goods, can determine more considerations before repurchasing the same service even being satisfied with prior experience. In the cases, when the above mentioned variables such as perceived risk or certainty (due to intangibility, for example) affects loyalty-satisfaction link as a moderator variables, then that relationship could be assigned to previously described 'mediator-moderator approach' by Tuu and Olsen (2016). The last but not less important approach, suggested by those authors, identifies that satisfaction-

loyalty(repeat patronage) link could be not only positive but also non-linear. This view was also supported in a previous research conducted by Ngobo (1999) and Finn (2012). The scholar Ngobo claimed that “there are minimum threshold to be reached for satisfaction to have greater positive effects on loyalty”. As well, the researcher has shown that linear relationship between satisfaction and loyalty could be mainly applied only in a particular segment of satisfaction or if customer do not have a huge amount of alternatives. However, such scholars as Lam (2014) have failed to find the evidence that if customer satisfaction is above a certain threshold, then customer loyalty (repeat patronage) is rapidly growing.

Furthermore, according to Szymanski and Henard (2001) it is important to note that ,for instance, satisfaction outcomes from loyalty perspective depends on various situation, product or service, because in each case both satisfaction and loyalty can have different antecedents. Moreover, satisfaction can reflect differently according the dimension of loyalty – intention to recommend, refusal of switching to other brand/supplier or actual repurchase behavior. Even more, while majority of authors in their literature review indicate that satisfaction positively influence customer intention to recommend preferable product or service, such scholars as Brown et al.(2005) has not seen the relation between customer satisfaction and intention to recommend.

To sum up, there are many different approaches to the role of satisfaction on customer loyalty such as perception that satisfaction is an essential variable of loyalty (Belas and Gabcova, 2016), only one of the main antecedents (Munari et al. 2013), or even some scholars do not indicated significant relation between those two variables as it was mentioned previously. Nevertheless, despite the contraries towards satisfaction clearly influence on customer loyalty in the marketing literature, majority of studies contributes to the approach which states that there is positive noticeable linkage on satisfaction-loyalty relation, thus our study will examine empirical research regarding this assumption.

Perceived service quality. The measurement of quality of service received a significant attention in nowadays academic literature related to the marketing field by various scholars. Kwok et al. (2015) indicated that service quality is the fulfilment of customer requirements by delivered service. In more details, it is widely confirmed that perceived service quality depends on the level of fulfilment of customer needs in compare with expectations for service performance. To broaden the concept of service quality, it is explained that there is various

aspects such as general content of service, staff, facilities, gained value that are evaluated by customer while perceiving service performance, thus, it could be assumed that service quality is a multidimensional concept (Chernatony and Harris, 2001). In addition, it is assumed that perception of service quality covers not only the functional performance of service, but also customer emotional, personal benefits that are gained from the particular service and while assessing the quality of service (Keller, 2003). In such terms, it could be claimed that while assessing customer perception of specific service quality, it is important to examine customer evaluation of quality of service towards the various dimensions. In other words, the higher compliance between customer's needs fulfilment and expectations, the higher customer satisfaction could be identified. Consequently, vice versa, if the distinction between customer expectations and received service performance is increased, it negatively effect the level of customer satisfaction which is a key element leading customer intentions to be loyal towards particular service. Generally, according to various authors it is broadly accepted that as there is a high positive linkage between perceived service quality and customer satisfaction, those concepts should be deeply measured while explaining customers behaviour or attitudinal loyalty (Fernandes et al., 2013; Annamdevula and Bellamkonda, 2014)

1.3. Factors having influence on loyalty intentions in higher education service

According to Ng, et al. (2009) the student can be also perceived as the consumer or customer, therefore, the existing literature on service loyalty could be relevant and applied as well in higher education context in which this paper aims to focus more deeply. Similarly to previously described researches based on customer loyalty, the explanation of **student loyalty** also faces with some distinctions towards the different authors studies. Generally, talking about the loyalty on service, Reichheld (2002) proposed the following explanation: "A loyal customer is one who values the relationship with the company enough to make the company as a preferred supplier. Loyal customers do not switch for small variations in price or service; instead they provide honest and constructive feedback, they consolidate the bulk of their category purchases with the company, they never abuse company personnel, and they provide enthusiastic referrals."

Thus, in higher education context, both dimensions behavioural and attitudinal are considered as the most appropriate way to explain student loyalty. Even though, many studies have been conducted regarding this issue, major disagreements come from interpretation how that behaviour and attitude should occur or maintain. For instance, researchers Blackmore, et al. (2006) suggest to perceive loyal students behavioural approach as repeatedly usage of university supplementary services, such as the library, catering or IT services, and attitudinal as intention to continue further studies (other degrees) at the same institution, as well as the willingness to recommend the institution to other persons. However, Mendez et al. (2009) agrees with the repurchasing the higher education service in the future, but perceives behavioural expression also as providing financial or non-financial support to the organization and retention within the studies period. To be more precisely, the author explains that student's strong positive attitudinal approach to the academic institution could subsequently be transferred into post-graduation loyalty which is described as belonging to alumni and ,accordingly, spreading a good word-of-mouth as well as providing financial contributions and job offers to graduated students. However, some researchers, for example as Austin et al., (2017) claims that it is better way to analyze student loyalty only from attitudinal side by stating that good recommendations towards the higher education institution better reflects positive and supportive approach compared to repeat purchases. In addition to that, other scholar Manzuma-Ndaaba (2015) also recognizes the belief that word-of-mouth communication appropriately demonstrates student loyalty, but ,in contract, emphasizes that it can result also in intention to take other or higher degree at the same education institution. Generally, nowadays student loyalty is perceived and defined not unambiguously in the existing literature based on business or educational service context. Nevertheless, as Pedro et al., (2016) point out in their recent research, it is significantly important to apply continuous measurements and observations of students willingness to recommend their educational institution or actual 'purchase' behaviour (retention, drop-outs or switching) during the studies and after graduation as it can contribute to understanding students intention to return and develop further relationship with their previous academic institution. Thus, our study, unfortunately, with some limitations in gathering relevant data about students attitude towards the educational service, aims to explore student loyalty referring to the willingness to recommend or study again (is perceived in our study as students 'likelihood to buy the same service again'') at their chosen education institution.

While talking about the higher education context, it has also generally been observed that even though such attribute as **satisfaction** does not unequivocally transfer into loyalty, it remains as one of the key elements influencing loyalty on goods or services in the most of researches (Taylor et al., 2004). However, despite the broad popularity among empirical studies in academic literature, the concept of satisfaction is perceived from different sides and interpretations by various authors. The attribute is associated by scholars not only with particular goods or services, but also with broaden aspects of company – personnel interactions or physical facilities. In more details, Douglas et al. (2006), revealed that the most important aspects leading student satisfaction are lectures content and positive education experience with the teachers. To be more precisely, most of the authors student overall satisfaction examine as a separate variable claiming that satisfaction with various educational service aspects such as study programme, teaching quality or personal growth and skills development could be explored as student **perceived service quality**. Service quality in education service is examined by various authors due to its high importance. Although, despite its high importance, there is still no exact definition of the concept as well as the uniqueness of elements defining educational service quality. Nevertheless, the most broadly definition of this concept is perceived as “the difference between what student expects to receive and his or her perception of actual service delivery” (Oneill and Palmer, 2004).

Finally, while talking about the academic institutions context, some researches also have shown that some student related factors could be also examined as having influence on student perception of educational service quality, satisfaction or loyalty. In more details, as Navarro et al. (2005) identified in the previous research, student satisfaction and perceived quality of educational service may vary depending on the type or length of **courses** stating that in a short period, different aspects of educational service could be less relevant or student might be less interacted with service, thus they could be less valued as well. The same effect could appear in terms of **lectures attendance**. In addition, on contrary, Melchor and Bravo (2012) findings showed that level of satisfaction with the learning experience decrease over time and that further attention should be paid on this variable while modelling students evaluations of educational experience. In terms of **level of education (study degree)**, Abdul et al. (2004) revealed in their research that student postgraduates showed more positive perception towards the academic experience compared to undergraduate students. In addition, taking into account an educational service evaluation in different kind educational institutions which providing different **disciplines**

or fields as well as exploring bachelor or postgraduate levels was suggested by the authors Perez and Torres (2016) as it was revealed that it might provide more detailed results in terms of student satisfaction and loyalty intentions. Similar findings regarding above mention factors were suggested by other authors as well (Helgesen and Nettet, 2007). Moreover, as Student Experience Survey conducted by Times Higher Education Journal (2012) revealed, students from law courses demonstrated more positive educational experience in higher education institutions in compare students from medicine, dentistry or undergraduate programmes related to technology, engineering or maths. The dissimilarities were identified as caused by the natural differences in teaching methods, studies content or approach.

However, despite variety of factors appear to differ in authors researches regarding the student perception of educational service quality, satisfaction or loyalty, there are lack of researches regarding the above mentioned variables. Thus, following above dissimilarities, our study will be set to examine those variables in more details.

1.4. Relation between satisfaction, perceived service quality elements impact and student loyalty in higher education service

In the marketing field of existing literature, higher education institutions are mainly perceived as an extended duration service and students are accordingly interpreted as clients or customer. There are many studies conducted by exploring the possible antecedents of loyalty on educational service. However, some distinctions between authors approach which set of components should be emphasized while reflecting student loyalty are observed.

For a greater visibility, Table 2 bellow represents the major researches conducted by various scholars towards the antecedents of students loyalty.

Table 2: Major studies on loyalty antecedents in higher education

Authors	Antecedents	Context (country or additional attributes of conducted research)
Caruana Albert , (2002)	Service quality Student satisfaction	India
Navarro, Mercedes Marzo Iglesias, Marta Pedraja Torres, Pilar Rivera, (2005)	Satisfaction with teaching methods Satisfaction with administration Satisfaction with teaching staff Satisfaction with enrolment Satisfaction with infrastructures	Spain
Ford, John B Joseph, Mathew Joseph, Beatriz, (2005)	Perceived service quality Student satisfaction	New Zealand, USA, Business school students
Helgesen, Øyvind Nesset, Erik, (2007)	Satisfaction Image of University College Image of study programme	Norway
Alves, Helena Raposo, Mario, (2007)	Student's global satisfaction in Higher Education Institution image	Portugal
Helgesen, Øyvind Nesset, Erik, (2007)	Satisfaction Reputation	Norway
Brown, Robert M. Mazzarol, Timothy William, (2009)	Satisfaction (emotional, evaluative) Perceived value Image Service quality- hardware Service quality - humanware	Australia

Rojas-Méndez, José I. Vasquez-Parraga, Arturo Z. Kara, Ali Cerde-Urrutia, Arcadio, (2009)	Commitment Trust Satisfaction Perceived service quality	Latin America
Mahadzirah, Mohamad Zainudin, Awang, (2009)	Student satisfaction Service quality Corporate image	Malaysia
Thomas, Sam, (2011)	Student satisfaction(with academic learning, support service, social life, administration, infrastructure) Institution reputation	India
Fernandes, Cedwyn Ross, Kieran Meraj, Mohammad, (2013)	Overall programme satisfaction Satisfaction with services and facilities	United Arab Emirates
Ali, Faizan Zhou, Yuan Hussain, Kashif Nair, Pradeep Kumar Ragavan, Neethiahnanthan Ari, (2016)	Student satisfaction (academic aspects, non-academic aspects, programme issues, reputation, access) Higher institution image	Malaysia

In more details, exploring the impact of perceived service quality on satisfaction and loyalty, Fernandes et al. (2013) by investigating student satisfaction with **teaching quality**, assessment, **academic support**, programme management and other facilities such as library, has found that factors leading overall student satisfaction were three of them - teaching quality, academic support and programme management. Other author Austin (2017) in his recent research explored satisfaction with such aspect as: college administration, discipline and values,

courses and instruction, skill developments, harmony in learning process and other college facilities, and the results showed that all mentioned aspects except college facilities (campus life, activities offered by college and etc.) were significantly influencing student satisfaction as well as loyalty. To be more precisely, the highest influence on student's loyalty was observed by satisfaction with courses and instruction, and satisfaction with skills developments. In addition, as it was claimed in BC College and Institute Student Outcomes journal (2002) after conducting a survey where former students were asked to evaluate their overall satisfaction with studies in line with their educational experience from skills development (analytical, communication, social skills), personal growth to quality of teaching and curriculum, it was observed that students from some particular study programs such as health-related study programmes showed higher scores in satisfaction with studies. Moreover, it was identified that curriculum content was a critical dimension explaining students overall satisfaction. Furthermore, it was claimed that student relevant abilities to develop their analytical skills, could also help to maintain better higher satisfaction scores. To generalize, it could be assumed that wider explorations of satisfaction aspects could report more accurate results about the drivers that could encourage students to be loyal towards the organization. Moreover, literature suggests that student satisfaction is not determined solely by the students' teaching and learning experiences but rather by their overall experiences towards the organization.

Furtherly, while talking about the satisfaction-loyalty relationship in an education service, it was assumed due to those conducted researches, that satisfied students are tend to transfer into loyalty students and later on perform as an advocates of the institution as well as make repeat purchasers such as taking another degree or other services at the same institution (Austin, 2017). In other words, as Helgessen and Nettet (2007);Mazadzirah (2009); Thomas (2011) and other authors stated in their study – satisfaction is perceived as a key and the most important factor of student loyalty. However, on contrary, Pham and Lai (2016) identified that the relationship between student commitment and loyalty were even stronger then the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty. It could be explained by student consideration of high importance of emotional attachments to the institution or beliefs that it is valuable for the future prosperity. In addition, such scholars as Rojas-Méndez et al. (2009) have also proved in their research that commitment is the most influential factor of the loyalty. The authors asserted that “the other factors have only indirect effects on loyalty and direct relationships in the following sequence: perceived service quality to satisfaction, satisfaction to trust, and trust to

commitment". However, describing in more details perceived service quality role, according to the previous studies, despite the widely confirmed positive relations between educational service quality, satisfaction and loyalty (Thomas, 2011), it was also recognised that satisfaction could play a **mediating role** in the relationship between perceived educational service quality and loyalty intentions. In other words, satisfaction could have direct and indirect impact on student loyalty intentions (Annamdevula et al., 2014). The research findings in the context of Indian universities, showed that perceived education service quality has a key impact on student satisfaction and loyalty. The similar findings was also supported by other author Lam et al. (2004) which also identified mediating effect of satisfaction on loyalty intentions.

To broaden the majors findings and outcomes of the researches in the education service, the authors of above described studies not only showed the importance of taking into consideration antecedents such as satisfaction, perceived quality or other variables as trust, shared values, commitment, institution reputations, but also suggested to explore the influence of in the previous chapter mentioned **study field, level of education, course or lectures attendance** because those additional factors could explain students behaviour towards loyalty intentions more clearly, but yet are explored only in specific study area or study courses (Brown and Mazarol, 2008).

To sum up the chapter, although a number of researches are accomplished among the service quality-satisfaction-student loyal linkage, according to Fernandes (2013) in order to obtain better understanding, explanation and identify the variety of students loyalty, other important variables - type of faculty (subject area), level of education - should be also included in line with satisfaction in the further analyses. To be more precisely, the authors suggest that relation between service quality, satisfaction and loyalty could also vary in different faculty's, degree or course of the same higher education institution.

2. METHODOLOGY OF DATA ANALYSIS ON FACTORS INFLUENCING STUDENT LOYALTY

2.1. Research problem, aim and objectives

In this chapter stated research problem, aim and objectives will be presented and discussed to a greater extent. Furtherly, research hypotheses, methods used for data collection and selected variables for the analysis in line with research limitations will be described in more details. In the analysis of scientific literature related to antecedents of student loyalty in higher education service it was revealed that various organization process, student or particular environment related factors have influence on loyalty (Helgesen and Nettet, 2007; Nevzat et al., 2016; Wong, 2016). However, considerable distinctions between authors approach which set of components of satisfaction should be emphasized while reflecting student loyalty are observed. At the same time, despite numerous studies that acknowledged the importance of student satisfaction on loyalty measurement in the higher education service context, researchers also suggested to explore the impact of factors such as gender, age, expectations or average grade point on loyalty behaviour as there are only few studies towards those aspects (Brokaw et al. 2004; Kwok et al. 2016).

Research problem – What relationship is between perceived educational service quality as well as overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions in higher education sector? Does different level of education, study course, lecture attendance and field of study has different loyalty and satisfaction scores?

The aim of research – to evaluate the impact of various perceived educational service quality elements on overall student satisfaction and loyalty in higher education institutions as well as analyse the impact level of education, study course, lecture attendance and field of study on students loyalty and satisfaction scores.

2.2. Research model and hypotheses

In this section, the hypothesized model (Figure 2 below illustrates the hypothesized model of this research based on the accumulative analysis of the relevant scientific literature) and hypothesis of the research will be discussed to a greater extent. Detailed description of the hypotheses will be stated on theoretical basis of this paper.

Figure 2 – Research Framework/Model

As it was discussed in theoretical analysis, some student related factors could be also examined as having influence on student perception of educational service quality, satisfaction or loyalty. As Navarro et al. (2005) identified in the previous research, perceived quality of educational service may vary depending on the type or length of courses stating that in a short period, different aspects of educational service could be less relevant or student might be less interacted with service, thus they could be less valued as well. The same effect might appear in the terms of level of education (study degree) or lectures attendance. In addition, the authors Perez and Torres (2016) also suggested exploring different disciplines or fields as well as exploring bachelor or postgraduate levels while examining various aspects of perception of educational service. Hence, the previous findings suggest raising the following hypothesis:

H1: There is a significant effect of type of studies field on student perception of educational service quality elements:

H1-a: There is a significant effect of type of studies field on quality perception of course content

H1-b: There is a significant effect of type of studies field on quality perception of teaching

H1-c: There is a significant effect of type of studies field on encouragement to express personal opinion

H1-d: There is a significant effect of type of studies field on development of analytical thinking skills

H1-e: There is a significant effect of type of studies field on development of critical thinking skills

H2: There is a significant effect of type of education level on student perception of educational service quality elements:

H2-a: There is a significant effect of type of education level on quality perception of course content

H2-b: There is a significant effect of type of education level on quality perception of teaching

H2-c: *There is a significant effect of type of education level on encouragement to express personal opinion*

H2-d: *There is a significant effect of type of education level on development of analytical thinking skills*

H2-e: *There is a significant effect of type of education level on development of critical thinking skills*

H3: *There is a significant effect of type of study course on student perception of educational service quality elements:*

H3-a: *There is a significant effect of study course level on quality perception of course content*

H3-b: *There is a significant effect of study course on quality perception of teaching*

H3-c: *There is a significant effect of study course on encouragement to express personal opinion*

H3-d: *There is a significant effect of type of study course on development of analytical thinking skills*

H3-e: *There is a significant effect of type of study course on development of critical thinking skills*

H4: *There is a significant effect of level of lectures attendance on student perception of educational service quality elements:*

H4-a: *There is a significant effect of level of lectures attendance on quality perception of course content*

H4-b: *There is a significant effect of level of lectures attendance on quality perception of teaching*

H4-c: *There is a significant effect of level of lectures attendance on encouragement to express personal opinion*

H4-d: *There is a significant effect of level of lectures attendance on development of analytical thinking skills*

H4-e: *There is a significant effect of level of lectures attendance on development of critical thinking skills*

Also in the theoretical part of this paper Navarro et al. (2005) revealed that such factors as chosen studies field, level of education, course or lectures attendance have impact on students satisfaction (Helgesen and Nettet, 2007). Thus it is important to examine their influence in the mix of factors that effect satisfaction rates and correspondingly – student loyalty intention (The annual BC College and Institute Student Outcomes Survey, 2002). In addition, as Student Experience Survey conducted by Times Higher Education Journal (2012) revealed, students from law courses demonstrated more positive educational experience in higher education institutions in compare students from medicine, dentistry or undergraduate programmes related to technology, engineering or maths. The dissimilarities were identified as caused by the natural differences in teaching methods, studies content or approach. Hence, the previous findings suggest exploring the differences between student satisfaction and loyalty in terms of different studies field, course, level of education or lectures attendance raising the following hypothesis:

H5-a: *Students from social and humanitarian studies have significantly higher overall satisfaction scores than physical and biomedical studies.*

H5-b: *Students from social and humanitarian studies have significantly higher loyalty scores than physical and biomedical studies.*

H6-a: *Master students have significantly higher overall satisfaction scores than bachelor and integrated studies students in high education sector*

H6-b: *Master students have significantly higher loyalty scores than bachelor and integrated studies students in high education sector*

H7-a: *Higher course students have significantly higher overall satisfaction scores than lower course students*

H7-b: *Higher course students have significantly higher loyalty scores than lower course students*

H8: *Students with high level of lectures attendance have significantly higher overall satisfaction scores than low level of lectures attendance. (Hypothesis is tested only with Sample 1)*

Moreover, in the theoretical background it was revealed that the concept of satisfaction is perceived from different sides and interpretations by various authors among empirical studies in academic literature. However, Fernandes et al. (2013) by investigating student satisfaction with teaching quality, assessment, academic support, programme management and other facilities such as library, has found that the most significant factors leading overall student satisfaction were three of them - teaching quality, academic support and personal growth. All the variables were positively related with the students overall satisfaction. Thus, based on previous researches the following hypotheses were applied:

H9-a: *Satisfaction with perceived course content has positive impact on student overall satisfaction in higher education institutions*

H9-b: *Satisfaction with perceived quality of teaching has positive impact on student overall satisfaction in higher education institutions*

H9-c: *Satisfaction with expression of personal opinion during the studies (personal growth) has positive impact on student overall satisfaction in higher education institutions*

H9-d: *Satisfaction with development of analytical thinking skills during the studies (personal growth) has positive impact on student overall satisfaction in higher education institutions*

H9-e: *Satisfaction with development of critical thinking skills during the studies (personal growth) has positive impact on student overall satisfaction in higher education institutions*

Furtherly, as it was discussed in theoretical analysis, despite numerous studies towards the relationship between student satisfaction and loyalty from different perspectives and points of view, it was assumed that satisfied students are tend to transfer into loyalty students and later on perform as an advocates of the institution as well as make repeat purchasers such as taking another degree or other services at the same institution (Austin, 2017). In other words, as Helgesen and Nettet (2007); Mazadzirah (2009); Thomas (2011) and other authors stated in their study – satisfaction is perceived as a key and the most important positively related factor of student loyalty. Due to this theory background the first hypothesis was developed:

H10: *Student overall satisfaction in studies has positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions*

Furthermore, according to Helgesen et al. (2007), student perceived educational service quality is highly related with student overall satisfaction, motivation and greater loyalty intentions. Thus, it can be assumed that higher perceived educational service quality will have higher student intention to be loyal. It is highly admitted that improvement of perceived service quality scores lead directly to desirable outcomes regarding the student loyalty concept. Hence, the previous findings suggest raising the following hypothesis:

H11-a: *Satisfaction with perceived course content has positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions*

H11-b: *Satisfaction with perceived quality of teaching has positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions*

H11-c: *Satisfaction with expression of personal opinion during the studies (personal growth) has positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions*

H11-d: *Satisfaction with development of analytical thinking skills during the studies (personal growth) has positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions*

H11-e: *Satisfaction with development of critical thinking skills during the studies (personal growth) has positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions*

Moreover, according to the previous studies, despite the widely confirmed positive relations between educational service quality, satisfaction and loyalty (Thomas, 2011), it was also recognised that satisfaction could play a mediating role in the relationship between perceived educational service quality and loyalty intentions. In other words, satisfaction could have direct and indirect impact on student loyalty intentions (Annamdevula et al., 2014). The research findings in the context of Indian universities, showed that perceived education service quality has a key impact on student satisfaction and loyalty. The similar findings was also supported by other author Lam et al. (2004) which also identified mediating effect of satisfaction on loyalty intentions. Hence, the previous findings suggest raising the following hypothesis:

H12: *Elements of service quality has indirect (towards overall satisfaction) and direct impact on students loyalty (Hypothesis is tested only with Sample 2)*

Consequently, in order to examine the validation of the hypotheses, various methods of analysis for selected variables will be applied.

2.3. Methods of data collection and analysis

In this section selected data collection and analysis will be discussed in more detail. So that the aim of this paper will be implemented and for research execution purposes, the following data were used:

1. *University semi-annually survey data from January of 2014 year till June of 2016 year.*

This survey data represented student responses from the different faculties, study programmes, course and degrees at the university. Total sample size consists of 43691 observations.(Sample 1)

Defining measurement scales

Measurement scales consists of questions defined by hypothesis used to collect the required data for the study. As semi-annual student survey provides separate statements reflecting satisfaction with teaching quality, study content quality, critical thinking, analytical thing, expression of personal opinion as well as scores of students overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions. All the statements used in the study (except loyalty measurement, where dependent variable is dichotomous and measured by answering with NO/YES) were measured according to Likert five (5) point scale where 1 means Strongly disagree; 2 Disagree ; 3 Neither agree nor disagree; 4 Agree and 5 Strongly agree. All the measurement scales were already implied by the university database before the collecting data. The questionnaires are distributed online automatically via university official informational system at the end of each semester.

Sample 1 description

In order to achieve the research aims, in total 43691 respondents were included to the analysis. 28,5 % of the respondents were from humanitarian studies, 39,1 % of the respondents were from social studies, 18,1 % -physical studies, 14,3 – biomedical studies. Of all the respondents 65,7 % are from bachelor degree studies, 13,4 % from master degree studies and 20,6 % from integrated studies (type of the studies when students are automatically continuing master studies after finishing bachelor degree – such as law or medicine study programmes). Moreover, respondents included into the analysis were from 6 different study courses – from the 1st course (27,4 %), 2nd course (24,6%), 3rd course (19,5 %), 4th course (20,8%), 5th course (5,2 %), 6th course (2,5 %). Finally, as one of the aim in the analysis were to examine differences of perception of educational service quality, satisfaction and student loyalty intentions in terms of different level of lecture attendance by students, respondents from 4 different levels of lecture attendance were included into the analysis – 2,9 % of respondents attended 0 - 25 % of lectures,

5,8 % attended 26 – 50 % of lectures, 24,3 % attended 51 – 75 % of lectures and 64,3 % of respondents attended 76 – 100 % of lectures.

TABLE 3: Summary of sample profile of respondents

		Count	Column N%
Field of study	Humanitarian studies	12442	28,5
	Social studies	17085	39,1
	Physical studies	7928	18,1
	Biomedical studies	6236	14,3
Name of faculty	Faculty of Economics	7333	16,8
	Faculty of Philology	3817	8,7
	Faculty of Philosophy	3738	8,6
	Faculty of Physics	2262	5,2
	Faculty of History	1698	3,9
	Kaunas Humanitarian Faculty	2377	5,4
	Faculty of Communication	3415	7,8
	Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics	5666	13
	Faculty of Medicine	6236	14,3
	Institute of International Relations and Political Science	1896	4,3
	Faculty of Law	4441	10,2
	Faculty of Foreign Languages	812	1,9
Level of Education	Bachelor studies	28703	65,7
	Master studies	5835	13,4
	Integrated studies	8989	20,6
Study course	1 st course	11971	27,4
	2 nd course	10729	24,6
	3 rd course	8526	19,5
	4 th course	9085	20,8
	5 th course	2287	5,2
	6 th course	1091	2,5
Level of	0 - 25 %	1276	2,9

lectures	26 – 50 %	2553	5,8
attendance	51 – 75 %	10602	24,3
	76 – 100 %	28106	64,3

Defining methods of analysis

The initial stage is implemented based on quantitative research according to the relevant literature review. ANOVA analysis were conducted in order to identify the general differences between various elements of perceived service quality, satisfaction and loyalty scores in different field of studies, level of education, course and lectures attendance. In order to measure student loyalty, questions - ‘willingness to recommend chosen study programme to your friend or fellow’ (dichotomous variable) – were analysed in the research. Consequently, in order to measure different relations within perceived service quality, overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions as it was suggested in the research - logistic regression were implemented.

2. University semi-annually survey data from June of 2016 year till January of 2017 year.

This survey data represented student responses from the different faculties, study programmes, course and degrees at the university. Total sample size consists of 11414 observations.(Sample 2)

Defining measurement scales

Measurement scales consists of questions defined by hypothesis used to collect the required data for the study. As semi-annual student survey provides separate statements reflecting satisfaction with teaching quality, study content quality, critical thinking, analytical thing, expression of personal opinion as well as scores of students overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions. All the statements used in the study were measured according to Likert five (5) point scale where 1 means Strongly disagree; 2 Disagree ; 3 Neither agree nor disagree; 4 Agree and 5 Strongly agree. All the measurement scales were already implied by the university database before the collecting data. The questionnaires are distributed online automatically via university official informational system at the end of each semester.

Sample 2 description.

In order to achieve the research aims, in total 11414 respondents were included to the analysis. 25 % of the respondents were from humanitarian studies, 33,4 % of the respondents were from social studies, 19,6 % -physical studies, 19,8 % – biomedical studies. Of all the respondents 67,9 % are from bachelor degree studies, 13,3 % from master degree studies and 18,8 % from integrated studies (type of the studies when students are automatically continuing master studies after finishing bachelor degree – such as law or medicine study programmes). Moreover, respondents included into the analysis were from 6 different study courses – from the 1st course (37,6 %), 2nd course (23,7%), 3rd course (22,8 %), 4th course (11,4%), 5th course (2,3 %), 6th course (0,3 %). However, in this sample, data of the student lectures attendance was not provided, thus, consequently this independent categorical variable was not examined using this sample.

TABLE 4: Summary of sample profile of respondents

		Count	Column N%
Field of study	Humanitarian studies	2851	25
	Social studies	3815	33,4
	Physical studies	2242	19,6
	Biomedical studies	2260	19,8
Name of faculty	Faculty of Chemistry	442	3,9
	Faculty of Economics	1560	13,7
	Faculty of Philology	882	7,7
	Faculty of Philosophy	896	7,9
	Faculty of Physics	507	4,4
	Faculty of Natural Science	771	6,8
	Faculty of History	418	3,7
	Kaunas Humanitarian Faculty	462	4
	Faculty of Communication	772	6,8
	Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics	1293	11,3
	Faculty of Medicine	1489	13
The Center of Oriental Studies	119	1	

	Religious Studies and Research Center	6	0,1
	International Programs and Communications Division	121	1,1
	Institute of International Relations and Political Science	441	3,9
	Faculty of Law	1042	9,1
	Faculty of Foreign Languages	193	1,7
Level of Education	Bachelor studies	7755	67,9
	Master studies	1514	13,3
	Integrated studies	2145	18,8
Study course	1 st course	4295	37,6
	2 nd course	2710	23,7
	3 rd course	2601	22,8
	4 th course	1303	11,4
	5 th course	265	2,3
	6 th course	35	0,3

Defining methods of analysis

The initial stage is implemented based on quantitative research according to the relevant literature review. ANOVA analysis, Pearson's correlations and MANOVA were conducted in order to identify the general differences and correlations between various elements of perceived service quality, satisfaction and loyalty scores in different field of studies, level of education, course. In order to measure student loyalty intentions - 'If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university' question were included and examined in the analysis. Consequently, in order to measure different relations within perceived service quality, overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions as it was suggested in the research - multiple regressions were implemented.

2.4. Research limitations

Although, collected survey panel provides relevant data regarding students loyalty intentions (the questionnaire consisting of 55105 respondents (students form different faculty's, study programmes, courses or degree) where one of the survey question identifying student

loyalty intention - 'willingness to recommend chosen study programme to your friend or fellow' or 'If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university' was conducted), various aspects of perceived educational service quality and overall satisfaction, the database of university semi-annual questionnaires did not provide students demographic data. Moreover, the investigation in this paper was limited only by the information that was lawfully provided. Student surveys were covered only by the period from 2014 to 2017 academic year.

3. FACTORS INFLUENCING STUDENT LOYALTY IN HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR

3.1 Educational service quality perception in different study field, level of education and course (ANOVA analysis)

According to Navarro et al. (2005) the previous research showed that perceived quality of educational service may vary depending on the type or length of courses as, for instance, in a short studies period, different aspects of educational service could be less relevant or student might be less interacted with service, thus it could be less valued and perceived not so well in compare with those students who are more interacted with the educational service while studying for a longer period. The same effect might appear in the terms of level of education (study degree) or lectures attendance. In addition, the authors Perez and Torres (2016) also suggested exploring different disciplines or fields as well as exploring bachelor or postgraduate levels while examining various aspects of perception of educational service.

Thus, as the initial stage, repeated ANOVA analysis was performed in order to identify the differences of various elements of educational service quality perception in different study field, level of education, course and lectures attendance and to test **H1 – H4** hypotheses. The analysis was conducted using both data samples – *Sample 1* and *Sample 2*.

The results of one-way ANOVA (*Sample 1*) proved that some categories of students differ from one another in term of **quality perception of course content**. As the first step of the analysis, the interaction between different study field and quality perception of course content was tested and the results showed that there is a difference between these groups (*study fields*) in terms of quality perception of courses content ($F= 77.130, p<0.05$). Scheffe test indicated that there is a significant difference in scores of quality of courses content between all study fields, except between the following groups - Physical ($m=3,73$) and Biomedical science ($m=3,73$). Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 5. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field and quality perception of course content

Descriptives				
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	12070	3,92	1,001	0,009
<i>Social studies</i>	16563	3,81	1,062	0,008
<i>Physical studies</i>	7560	3,73	1,017	0,012
<i>Biomedical studies</i>	6071	3,73	1,053	0,014
Total	42254	3,82	1,024	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	241,340	3	80,447	77,130	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	44067,029	42250	1,043		
<i>Total</i>	44308,369	42253			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>Field of studies</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	<i>"Social Studies"</i>	,110*	0,012	0,000
	<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	,190*	0,015	0,000
	<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	,199*	0,016	0,000
<i>"Social Studies"</i>	<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	-,110*	0,012	0,000
	<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	,080*	0,014	0,000
	<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	,088*	0,015	0,000
<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	-,190*	0,015	0,000
	<i>"Social Studies"</i>	-,080*	0,014	0,000
	<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	0,009	0,018	0,972
<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	-,199*	0,016	0,000
	<i>"Social Studies"</i>	-,088*	0,015	0,000
	<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	-0,009	0,018	0,972

Furtherly, repeated one-way ANOVA was performed to test the differences in various *levels of education* (study degree), course of studies and lectures attendance in terms of **quality perception of course content**. The results of one-way ANOVA showed that there are no significant differences in the interaction between respondents who studies in Bachelor (m=3,82), Master(m=3,79) and Integrated studies degree(m=3,83) in terms of perceived quality of courses content (F=2.309, p=0.099). In addition, according to the results, the interaction between different *study courses* and **quality perception of course content** scores showed that there are differences between respondents who studies in 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th course in terms of perceived quality of courses content (F=152,859, p<0.05). Scheffe test indicated that there is a significant difference in scores of quality of courses content between all study courses, except between the following ones - 5th (m=3,79) and 2nd (m=3,85); 5th (m=3,79) and 3rd (m=3,71) ; 5th (m=3,79) and 4th (m=3,71) ; 3rd (m=3,71) and 4th (m=3,71). Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 6. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different levels (degree) of studies and perception of quality of courses content

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>Bachelor studies</i>	27864	3,82	1,016	0,006
<i>Master studies</i>	5512	3,79	1,052	0,014
<i>Integrated studies</i>	8725	3,83	1,032	0,011
<i>Total</i>	42101	3,82	1,024	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	4,842	2	2,421	2,309	0,099
<i>Within Groups</i>	44133,737	42098	1,048		
<i>Total</i>	44138,579	42100			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Level of education</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	0,023	0,015	0,319
	<i>Vn</i>	-0,015	0,013	0,488
<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	-0,023	0,015	0,319
	<i>Vn</i>	-0,038	0,018	0,099
<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	0,015	0,013	0,488
	<i>M</i>	0,038	0,018	0,099

Table 7. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different course of studies and perception of quality of courses content

Descriptives				
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>1st course</i>	11923	3,99	0,940	0,009
<i>2nd course</i>	10465	3,85	1,001	0,010
<i>3rd course</i>	8472	3,71	1,036	0,011
<i>4th course</i>	8388	3,71	1,082	0,012
<i>5th course</i>	2124	3,79	1,046	0,023
<i>6th course</i>	882	3,30	1,196	0,040
<i>Total</i>	42254	3,82	1,024	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	787,323	5	157,465	152,859	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	43521,046	42248	1,030		
<i>Total</i>	44308,369	42253			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Study Course</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>1 course</i>	<i>2 course</i>	,143 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	,281 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,276 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	,196 [*]	0,024	0,000
	<i>6 course</i>	,686 [*]	0,035	0,000
<i>2 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,143 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	,138 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,133 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	0,053	0,024	0,443
	<i>6 course</i>	,543 [*]	0,036	0,000
<i>3 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,281 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,138 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	-0,005	0,016	1,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-,085 [*]	0,025	0,035
	<i>6 course</i>	,405 [*]	0,036	0,000
<i>4 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,276 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,133 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	0,005	0,016	1,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-0,080	0,025	0,060
	<i>6 course</i>	,410 [*]	0,036	0,000
<i>5 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,196 [*]	0,024	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-0,053	0,024	0,443
	<i>3 course</i>	,085 [*]	0,025	0,035
	<i>4 course</i>	0,080	0,025	0,060
	<i>6 course</i>	,490 [*]	0,041	0,000
<i>6 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,686 [*]	0,035	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,543 [*]	0,036	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	-,405 [*]	0,036	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	-,410 [*]	0,036	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-,490 [*]	0,041	0,000

Furthermore, according to the results of one-way ANOVA testing the interaction between different level of *lectures attendance* and **perception of course content** scores showed that there are significant differences between all the respondent groups who attended 0-25% (m=3,21), 26-50% (m=3,43), 51%-75% (m=3,66) and 76%-100% (m=3,94) of lectures in terms of quality

perception of course content ($F=505,980$, $p<0.05$). Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 8. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different levels of lectures attendance and perception of course content

Descriptives				
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>0-25 proc.</i>	1230	3,21	1,270	0,036
<i>26-50 proc.</i>	2536	3,43	1,088	0,022
<i>51-75 proc.</i>	10547	3,66	1,012	0,010
<i>76-100%</i>	27941	3,94	0,983	0,006
Total	42254	3,82	1,024	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	1536,684	3	512,228	505,980	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	42771,685	42250	1,012		
Total	44308,369	42253			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Lectures attendance</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	-,220*	0,035	0,000
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	-,451*	0,030	0,000
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	-,733*	0,029	0,000
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	,220*	0,035	0,000
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	-,231*	0,022	0,000
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	-,514*	0,021	0,000
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	,451*	0,030	0,000
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	,231*	0,022	0,000
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	-,283*	0,011	0,000
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	,733*	0,029	0,000
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	,514*	0,021	0,000
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	,283*	0,011	0,000

In addition, to the analysis of differences in **quality perception of course content**, further aspects of perceived educational service quality such as **teaching quality perception, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills** in terms of **different study field, level of education, course and lectures attendance** were explored as well using one-way ANOVA. The results also proved that some categories of students differ from one another in terms above.

According to the results of ANOVA, there is a significant difference between all *studies field* - Humanitarian studies, Social studies, Physical studies, Biomedical studies in terms of **perception of teaching quality** ($F=169,983$, $p<0.05$). Scores in perception of teaching quality tend to be significantly higher in Humanitarian studies ($m=3.86$) compared to Biomedical studies ($m=3.54$). Other fields of studies as Scheffe test demonstrates, also differ significantly between each other ($p<0.05$). Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 9. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different field of studies and perception of teaching quality

Descriptives				
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
"Humanitarian Studies"	12068	3,86	0,986	0,009
"Social Studies"	16563	3,74	1,022	0,008
"Physical Studies"	7546	3,61	1,009	0,012
"Biomedical Studies"	6074	3,54	1,076	0,014
<i>Total</i>	42251	3,72	1,024	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	528,299	3	176,100	169,983	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	43767,128	42247	1,036		
<i>Total</i>	44295,427	42250			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Studies Field Classification</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	<i>"Social Studies"</i>	,127 [*]	0,012	0,000
	<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	,252 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	,319 [*]	0,016	0,000
<i>"Social Studies"</i>	<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	-,127 [*]	0,012	0,000
	<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	,125 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	,191 [*]	0,015	0,000
<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	-,252 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>"Social Studies"</i>	-,125 [*]	0,014	0,000
	<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	,067 [*]	0,018	0,002
<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	-,319 [*]	0,016	0,000
	<i>"Social Studies"</i>	-,191 [*]	0,015	0,000
	<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	-,067 [*]	0,018	0,002

In terms of different *level of education*, students demonstrate different scores in perception of teaching quality as well ($F=19,567$, $p<0.05$). The higher scores in terms of perception of teaching quality were observed between Bachelor studies students ($m=3.74$) and Master students ($m=3.73$) compared to Integrated studies students ($m=3.66$) which demonstrated the lowest scores in perception of teaching quality. However, as Scheffe test identified ($p=0,952$) there was no significant difference in perception of teaching quality between Bachelor studies students and Master degree students. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 10. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different levels of education and perception of teaching quality

Descriptives				
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>B</i>	27861	3,74	1,000	0,006
<i>M</i>	5511	3,73	1,044	0,014
<i>Vn</i>	8726	3,66	1,082	0,012
<i>Total</i>	42098	3,72	1,024	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	40,984	2	20,492	19,567	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	44084,870	42095	1,047		
<i>Total</i>	44125,854	42097			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Level of education</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	0,005	0,015	0,952
	<i>Vn</i>	,078*	0,013	0,000
<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	-0,005	0,015	0,952
	<i>Vn</i>	,073*	0,018	0,000
<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	-,078*	0,013	0,000
	<i>M</i>	-,073*	0,018	0,000

Moreover, in terms of different *study course*, students also demonstrate different scores in perception of teaching quality ($F=136,794$, $p<0.05$). The higher scores in terms of perception of teaching quality were observed between students from lower courses (1st-2nd courses; 1st course ($m=3.88$), 2nd course ($m=3.74$)) compared to students from higher courses (3rd – 6th courses; 3rd course ($m=3.62$), 4th course ($m=3.66$), 5th course ($m=3.65$) 6th course ($m=3.15$)) in perception of teaching quality. Scheffe test confirmed that between some categories there are significant

differences in terms of evaluation of teaching quality. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 11. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different study course and perception of teaching quality

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>1 course</i>	11925	3,88	0,933	0,009
<i>2 course</i>	10466	3,74	1,013	0,010
<i>3 course</i>	8472	3,62	1,031	0,011
<i>4 course</i>	8383	3,66	1,075	0,012
<i>5 course</i>	2124	3,65	1,087	0,024
<i>6 course</i>	881	3,15	1,195	0,040
<i>Total</i>	42251	3,72	1,024	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	705,743	5	141,149	136,794	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	43589,684	42245	1,032		
<i>Total</i>	44295,427	42250			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Study Course</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>1 course</i>	<i>2 course</i>	,142*	0,014	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	,257*	0,014	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,215*	0,014	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	,229*	0,024	0,000
	<i>6 course</i>	,727*	0,035	0,000
<i>2 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,142*	0,014	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	,115*	0,015	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,073*	0,015	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	,088*	0,024	0,022
	<i>6 course</i>	,585*	0,036	0,000
<i>3 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,257*	0,014	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,115*	0,015	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	-0,042	0,016	0,197
	<i>5 course</i>	-0,028	0,025	0,940
	<i>6 course</i>	,470*	0,036	0,000
<i>4 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,215*	0,014	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,073*	0,015	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	0,042	0,016	0,197
	<i>5 course</i>	0,015	0,025	0,996
	<i>6 course</i>	,512*	0,036	0,000
<i>5 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,229*	0,024	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,088*	0,024	0,022
	<i>3 course</i>	0,028	0,025	0,940
	<i>4 course</i>	-0,015	0,025	0,996
	<i>6 course</i>	,497*	0,041	0,000
<i>6 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,727*	0,035	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,585*	0,036	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	-,470*	0,036	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	-,512*	0,036	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-,497*	0,041	0,000

Furthermore, in terms of different level of *lectures attendance*, students also demonstrate different scores in perception of teaching quality ($F=373,812$, $p<0.05$). The higher scores in terms of perception of teaching quality were observed between students who participated in 51-75% of lectures ($m=3.57$) and 76-100% of lectures ($m=3.83$). Students that participated in a less amount of lectures demonstrated lower scores in perception of teaching quality (0-25%

attendance of lectures (m=3.20), 26-50% attendance of lectures (m=3.41)). Scheffe test confirmed that there are significant differences in terms of evaluation of teaching quality between all different categories of lectures attendance. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 12. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different level of lecture attendance and perception of teaching quality

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	1225	3,20	1,239	0,035
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	2535	3,41	1,064	0,021
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	10544	3,57	1,014	0,010
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	27947	3,83	0,993	0,006
<i>Total</i>	42251	3,72	1,024	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	1145,406	3	381,802	373,812	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	43150,021	42247	1,021		
<i>Total</i>	44295,427	42250			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Lectures attendance</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>-,206*</i>	<i>0,035</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,372*</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,629*</i>	<i>0,030</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,206*</i>	<i>0,035</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,166*</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,423*</i>	<i>0,021</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,372*</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,166*</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,257*</i>	<i>0,012</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,629*</i>	<i>0,030</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,423*</i>	<i>0,021</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>,257*</i>	<i>0,012</i>	<i>0,000</i>

In addition to the analysis above, ANOVA test was performed to identify differences in student perception regarding the **encouragement to express their personal opinion during the studies** in different study field, level of education, study course and lectures attendance. According to ANOVA results, there is a significant difference between all *studies field* - Humanitarian studies, Social studies, Physical studies, Biomedical studies in terms of encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies ($F=728,357$, $p<0.05$). Scores in encouragement to express student personal opinion during the studies tend to be significantly higher in Humanitarian studies ($m=4.12$) and Social studies ($m=3.92$) compared to Biomedical studies ($m=3.56$) and Physical studies ($m=3.54$). Scheffe test showed significant differences between all the categories except students who were from Biomedical studies and Physical studies ($p=0.625$). Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 13. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different field of studies and encouragement to express student personal opinion during the studies

Descriptives				
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
"Humanitarian Studies"	12062	4,12	0,941	0,009
"Social Studies"	16547	3,92	0,992	0,008
"Physical Studies"	7516	3,54	1,051	0,012
"Biomedical Studies"	6056	3,56	1,119	0,014
<i>Total</i>	42181	3,86	1,033	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	2218,962	3	739,654	728,357	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	42831,150	42177	1,016		
<i>Total</i>	45050,112	42180			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Studies Field Classification</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,200*	0,012	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	,585*	0,015	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,562*	0,016	0,000
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,200*	0,012	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	,385*	0,014	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,362*	0,015	0,000
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,585*	0,015	0,000
	"Social Studies"	-,385*	0,014	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	-0,023	0,017	0,625
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,562*	0,016	0,000
	"Social Studies"	-,362*	0,015	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	0,023	0,017	0,625

The results also indicated that significant differences were observed in different level of education, study course and lectures attendance in terms of to expression of personal opinion during the studies ($F=283,539$, $p<0.05$). In terms of different *level of education*, the higher scores in terms of expression of personal opinion during the studies were observed between Bachelor studies students ($m=3.87$) and Master students ($m=4.09$) compared to Integrated studies students ($m=3.68$) which demonstrated the lowest scores in encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies. As Scheffe test showed, there is significant different between all students groups – Bachelor, Master and Integrated studies students. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 14. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different level of education and encouragement to express student personal opinion during the studies

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>B</i>	27810	3,87	1,016	0,006
<i>M</i>	5510	4,09	0,956	0,013
<i>Vn</i>	8708	3,68	1,101	0,012
<i>Total</i>	42028	3,86	1,033	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	597,456	2	298,728	283,539	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	44276,258	42025	1,054		
<i>Total</i>	44873,714	42027			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Level of education</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	-,226*	0,015	0,000
	<i>Vn</i>	,192*	0,013	0,000
<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	,226*	0,015	0,000
	<i>Vn</i>	,418*	0,018	0,000
<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	-,192*	0,013	0,000
	<i>M</i>	-,418*	0,018	0,000

Moreover, in terms of different *study course*, students also demonstrate different scores in perception of encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies ($F=40,949$, $p<0.05$). high scores in terms of encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies were observed between almost all study courses (1st -6th courses; varying from $m=3.92$ to $m=3.79$). Lower scores in encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies were identified between student from 6th courses ($m=3.48$). However, Scheffe test showed that no all student groups differ in term of encouragement to express personal opinion. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 15. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different study course and encouragement to express student personal opinion during the studies

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>1 course</i>	11900	3,92	1,009	0,009
<i>2 course</i>	10446	3,88	1,034	0,010
<i>3 course</i>	8463	3,79	1,023	0,011
<i>4 course</i>	8367	3,84	1,047	0,011
<i>5 course</i>	2123	3,88	1,046	0,023
<i>6 course</i>	882	3,48	1,162	0,039
<i>Total</i>	42181	3,86	1,033	0,005

ANOVA					
Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	217,646	5	43,529	40,949	0,000
Within Groups	44832,467	42175	1,063		
Total	45050,112	42180			

Multiple Comparisons				
Dependent Variable:	Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.			
Scheffe				
(I) Study Course		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
1 course	2 course	0,042	0,014	0,101
	3 course	,128*	0,015	0,000
	4 course	,086*	0,015	0,000
	5 course	0,042	0,024	0,707
	6 course	,439*	0,036	0,000
2 course	1 course	-0,042	0,014	0,101
	3 course	,086*	0,015	0,000
	4 course	0,044	0,015	0,124
	5 course	0,000	0,025	1,000
	6 course	,397*	0,036	0,000
3 course	1 course	-,128*	0,015	0,000
	2 course	-,086*	0,015	0,000
	4 course	-0,041	0,016	0,238
	5 course	-,086*	0,025	0,037
	6 course	,311*	0,036	0,000
4 course	1 course	-,086*	0,015	0,000
	2 course	-0,044	0,015	0,124
	3 course	0,041	0,016	0,238
	5 course	-0,045	0,025	0,672
	6 course	,353*	0,037	0,000
5 course	1 course	-0,042	0,024	0,707
	2 course	0,000	0,025	1,000
	3 course	,086*	0,025	0,037
	4 course	0,045	0,025	0,672
	6 course	,397*	0,041	0,000
6 course	1 course	-,439*	0,036	0,000
	2 course	-,397*	0,036	0,000
	3 course	-,311*	0,036	0,000
	4 course	-,353*	0,037	0,000
	5 course	-,397*	0,041	0,000

Furthermore, in terms of different level of *lectures attendance*, students showed different scores in perception of encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies as well ($F=347,384$, $p<0.05$). The higher scores in encouragement to express personal opinion during the studies were observed between students who participated in 51-75% of lectures ($m=3.74$) and 76-100% of lectures ($m=3.96$). Students that participated in a less amount of lectures demonstrated lower scores in perception of teaching quality (0-25% attendance of lectures ($m=3.27$), 26-50% attendance of lectures ($m=3.55$)). Scheffe test showed that there was significant different between all student groups in encouragement to express personal opinion. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 16. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different level of lectures attendance and encouragement to express student personal opinion during the studies

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	1216	3,27	1,223	0,035
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	2533	3,55	1,040	0,021
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	10529	3,74	1,017	0,010
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	27903	3,96	1,011	0,006
<i>Total</i>	42181	3,86	1,033	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	1086,302	3	362,101	347,384	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	43963,810	42177	1,042		
<i>Total</i>	45050,112	42180			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Lectures attendance</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>-,278*</i>	<i>0,036</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,462*</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,684*</i>	<i>0,030</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,278*</i>	<i>0,036</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,184*</i>	<i>0,023</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,406*</i>	<i>0,021</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,462*</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,184*</i>	<i>0,023</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,222*</i>	<i>0,012</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,684*</i>	<i>0,030</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,406*</i>	<i>0,021</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>,222*</i>	<i>0,012</i>	<i>0,000</i>

Also, in order to identify differences in student perception regarding the **development of student analytical thinking skills** (encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies) in different study field, level of education, study course and lectures attendance ANOVA analysis were employed. According to ANOVA results, there is a significant difference between all *studies field* - Humanitarian studies, Social studies, Physical studies, Biomedical studies in terms of development of student analytical thinking skills during the studies ($F=302,512$, $p<0.05$). Scores in encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies s tend to be significantly higher in Humanitarian studies ($m=4.15$) and Social studies ($m=3.97$) compared to Biomedical studies ($m=3.71$) and Physical studies ($m=3.88$). Scheffe test showed that there was significant different between all student groups in terms of development of student analytical thinking skills. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 17. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different field of studies and encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies

Descriptives				
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>"Humanitarian Studies"</i>	12058	4,15	0,909	0,008
<i>"Social Studies"</i>	16546	3,97	0,970	0,008
<i>"Physical Studies"</i>	7531	3,88	0,989	0,011
<i>"Biomedical Studies"</i>	6062	3,71	1,073	0,014
<i>Total</i>	42197	3,97	0,983	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	857,759	3	285,920	302,512	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	39878,824	42193	0,945		
<i>Total</i>	40736,583	42196			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Studies Field Classification</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,179*	0,012	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	,276*	0,014	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,436*	0,015	0,000
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,179*	0,012	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	,096*	0,014	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,257*	0,015	0,000
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,276*	0,014	0,000
	"Social Studies"	-,096*	0,014	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,161*	0,017	0,000
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,436*	0,015	0,000
	"Social Studies"	-,257*	0,015	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	-,161*	0,017	0,000

The results also indicated that significant differences were observed in different level of education, study course and lectures attendance in terms of encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies ($p < 0.05$). In terms of different *level of education*, students showed different scores in perception of encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies ($F = 310,466$, $p < 0.05$). The higher scores in terms of encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies were observed between Bachelor studies students ($m = 3.98$) and Master students ($m = 4.19$) compared to Integrated studies students ($m = 3.78$) which demonstrated the lowest scores in encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies. Scheffe test showed that there was significant different between all student groups in terms of development of student analytical thinking skills. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 18. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different ;evel of education and encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies

Descriptives				
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>B</i>	27815	3,98	0,962	0,006
<i>M</i>	5517	4,19	0,905	0,012
<i>Vn</i>	8712	3,78	1,057	0,011
<i>Total</i>	42044	3,97	0,982	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	590,466	2	295,233	310,466	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	39978,272	42041	0,951		
<i>Total</i>	40568,737	42043			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Level of education</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	-,204*	0,014	0,000
	<i>Vn</i>	,207*	0,012	0,000
<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	,204*	0,014	0,000
	<i>Vn</i>	,411*	0,017	0,000
<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	-,207*	0,012	0,000
	<i>M</i>	-,411*	0,017	0,000

Moreover, in terms of different *study course*, students showed different scores in perception of encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies ($F=39,842$, $p<0.05$). The highest scores in terms of development of student analytical thinking skills during the studies were observed between 1st and 2nd study courses (1st course ($m=4.01$) ; 2nd course ($m=4.02$)). Lower scores in development of student analytical thinking skills during the studies were identified between students from 3rd -5th courses (means varying between $m=3.92$ to $m=3.95$). The lowest scores in development of student analytical thinking skills were observed in 6th study course with $m=3.61$. However, as Scheffe test indicated, not all groups of student differ in terms of perception of analytical skills development during the studies. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 19. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different study course and encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>1 course</i>	11900	4,01	0,959	0,009
<i>2 course</i>	10451	4,02	0,972	0,010
<i>3 course</i>	8464	3,93	0,966	0,010
<i>4 course</i>	8376	3,92	1,010	0,011
<i>5 course</i>	2125	3,95	1,012	0,022
<i>6 course</i>	881	3,61	1,132	0,038
<i>Total</i>	42197	3,97	0,983	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	191,438	5	38,288	39,842	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	40545,145	42191	0,961		
<i>Total</i>	40736,583	42196			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Study Course</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>1 course</i>	<i>2 course</i>	-0,005	0,013	1,000
	<i>3 course</i>	,080*	0,014	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,090*	0,014	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	0,067	0,023	0,132
	<i>6 course</i>	,404*	0,034	0,000
<i>2 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	0,005	0,013	1,000
	<i>3 course</i>	,085*	0,014	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,094*	0,014	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	0,072	0,023	0,089
	<i>6 course</i>	,408*	0,034	0,000
<i>3 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,080*	0,014	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,085*	0,014	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	0,009	0,015	0,996
	<i>5 course</i>	-0,013	0,024	0,998
	<i>6 course</i>	,323*	0,035	0,000
<i>4 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,090*	0,014	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,094*	0,014	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	-0,009	0,015	0,996
	<i>5 course</i>	-0,022	0,024	0,972
	<i>6 course</i>	,314*	0,035	0,000
<i>5 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-0,067	0,023	0,132
	<i>2 course</i>	-0,072	0,023	0,089
	<i>3 course</i>	0,013	0,024	0,998
	<i>4 course</i>	0,022	0,024	0,972
	<i>6 course</i>	,336*	0,039	0,000
<i>6 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,404*	0,034	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,408*	0,034	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	-,323*	0,035	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	-,314*	0,035	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-,336*	0,039	0,000

Furthermore, in terms of different level of *lectures attendance*, students showed different scores in perception of encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies ($F=298,113$, $p<0.05$). The higher scores in development of student analytical thinking skills during the studies were observed between students who participated in 51-75% of lectures ($m=3.88$) and 76-100% of lectures ($m=4.05$). Students that participated in a less amount of

lectures demonstrated lower scores in development of student analytical thinking skills (0-25% attendance of lectures (m=3.41), 26-50% attendance of lectures (m=3.70)). Scheffe test showed that there was significant different between all student groups in terms of development of student analytical thinking skills. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 20. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different lectures attendance and encouragement to analyze and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies

Descriptives				
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>1217</i>	<i>3,41</i>	<i>1,243</i>	<i>0,036</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>2531</i>	<i>3,70</i>	<i>1,010</i>	<i>0,020</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>10538</i>	<i>3,88</i>	<i>0,956</i>	<i>0,009</i>
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>27911</i>	<i>4,05</i>	<i>0,962</i>	<i>0,006</i>
<i>Total</i>	<i>42197</i>	<i>3,97</i>	<i>0,983</i>	<i>0,005</i>

ANOVA					
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	<i>845,546</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>281,849</i>	<i>298,113</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>Within Groups</i>	<i>39891,037</i>	<i>42193</i>	<i>0,945</i>		
<i>Total</i>	<i>40736,583</i>	<i>42196</i>			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Lectures attendance</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>-,291*</i>	<i>0,034</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,468*</i>	<i>0,029</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,643*</i>	<i>0,028</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,291*</i>	<i>0,034</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,176*</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,352*</i>	<i>0,020</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,468*</i>	<i>0,029</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,176*</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,175*</i>	<i>0,011</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,643*</i>	<i>0,028</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,352*</i>	<i>0,020</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>,175*</i>	<i>0,011</i>	<i>0,000</i>

Finally, in order to examine the differences in student perception regarding the **development of their critical thinking skills** (if students perceive that the content of study courses developed their critical thinking skills) in different study field, level of education, study course and lectures attendance ANOVA analysis were employed. According to ANOVA results, there is a significant difference between all *studies field* - Humanitarian studies, Social studies, Physical studies, Biomedical studies in terms of development of student critical thinking skills during the studies ($F=305,609$, $p<0.05$). Scores in development of critical thinking skills during the studies tend to be significantly higher in Humanitarian studies ($m=3.93$) and Social studies ($m=3.74$) compared to Biomedical studies ($m=3.44$) and Physical studies ($m=3.66$). Scheffe test

showed that there was significant different between all student groups in terms of development of student critical thinking skills. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 21. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different field of studies and students evaluation of development of critical thinking skills

Descriptives				
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
"Humanitarian Studies"	12039	3,93	1,037	0,009
"Social Studies"	16521	3,74	1,069	0,008
"Physical Studies"	7522	3,66	1,047	0,012
"Biomedical Studies"	6052	3,44	1,178	0,015
<i>Total</i>	42134	3,74	1,084	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	1054,828	3	351,609	305,540	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	48482,267	42130	1,151		
<i>Total</i>	49537,095	42133			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Studies Field Classification</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,190*	0,013	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	,275*	0,016	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,496*	0,017	0,000
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,190*	0,013	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	,085*	0,015	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,306*	0,016	0,000
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,275*	0,016	0,000
	"Social Studies"	-,085*	0,015	0,000
	"Biomedical Studies"	,221*	0,019	0,000
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,496*	0,017	0,000
	"Social Studies"	-,306*	0,016	0,000
	"Physical Studies"	-,221*	0,019	0,000

The results also indicated that significant differences were observed in different level of education, study course and lectures attendance in terms of development of critical thinking skills ($p < 0.05$). In terms of different *level of education*, students showed different scores in students perception of development of critical thinking skills ($F = 226,204$, $p < 0.05$). The higher scores in development of students' critical thinking skills during the studies were observed between Bachelor studies students ($m = 3.76$) and Master students ($m = 3.94$) compared to Integrated studies students ($m = 3.55$) which demonstrated the lowest scores in perception that the content of study courses developed their critical thinking skills.). Scheffe test showed that there was significant different between all student groups in terms of development of student critical thinking skills. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 22. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different level of education and students evaluation of development of critical thinking skills

Descriptives				
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>B</i>	27765	3,76	1,058	0,006
<i>M</i>	5511	3,94	1,047	0,014
<i>Vn</i>	8705	3,55	1,160	0,012
<i>Total</i>	41981	3,74	1,084	0,005

ANOVA					
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	526,046	2	263,023	226,204	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	48810,733	41978	1,163		
<i>Total</i>	49336,778	41980			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Level of education</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	-,182*	0,016	0,000
	<i>Vn</i>	,203*	0,013	0,000
<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	,182*	0,016	0,000
	<i>Vn</i>	,385*	0,019	0,000
<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	-,203*	0,013	0,000
	<i>M</i>	-,385*	0,019	0,000

Moreover, in terms of different *study course*, students also showed different scores in students perception of development of critical thinking skills ($F=23,394$, $p<0.05$). The highest scores in terms of development of student critical thinking skills during the studies were observed between 1st and 5th study courses (means varying between $m=3.70$ to $m=3.79$). Significantly lower scores in development of student critical thinking skills during the studies were identified between students from 6th course ($m=3.45$). However, as Scheffe test indicated, not all groups of student

differ in terms of perception of critical thinking skills development during the studies. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 23. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different study course and students evaluation of development of critical thinking skills

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>1 course</i>	11873	3,77	1,064	0,010
<i>2 course</i>	10436	3,79	1,073	0,011
<i>3 course</i>	8457	3,70	1,072	0,012
<i>4 course</i>	8364	3,70	1,110	0,012
<i>5 course</i>	2122	3,75	1,124	0,024
<i>6 course</i>	882	3,45	1,196	0,040
<i>Total</i>	42134	3,74	1,084	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	137,161	5	27,432	23,394	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	49399,934	42128	1,173		
<i>Total</i>	49537,095	42133			

Multiple Comparisons				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Study Course</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>1 course</i>	<i>2 course</i>	-0,024	0,015	0,727
	<i>3 course</i>	,066*	0,015	0,002
	<i>4 course</i>	,068*	0,015	0,002
	<i>5 course</i>	0,021	0,026	0,984
	<i>6 course</i>	,317*	0,038	0,000
<i>2 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	0,024	0,015	0,727
	<i>3 course</i>	,091*	0,016	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	,092*	0,016	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	0,046	0,026	0,681
	<i>6 course</i>	,341*	0,038	0,000
<i>3 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,066*	0,015	0,002
	<i>2 course</i>	-,091*	0,016	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	0,001	0,017	1,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-0,045	0,026	0,708
	<i>6 course</i>	,250*	0,038	0,000
<i>4 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,068*	0,015	0,002
	<i>2 course</i>	-,092*	0,016	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	-0,001	0,017	1,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-0,047	0,026	0,680
	<i>6 course</i>	,249*	0,038	0,000
<i>5 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-0,021	0,026	0,984
	<i>2 course</i>	-0,046	0,026	0,681
	<i>3 course</i>	0,045	0,026	0,708
	<i>4 course</i>	0,047	0,026	0,680
	<i>6 course</i>	,295*	0,043	0,000
<i>6 course</i>	<i>1 course</i>	-,317*	0,038	0,000
	<i>2 course</i>	-,341*	0,038	0,000
	<i>3 course</i>	-,250*	0,038	0,000
	<i>4 course</i>	-,249*	0,038	0,000
	<i>5 course</i>	-,295*	0,043	0,000

Furthermore, in terms of different level of *lectures attendance*, students showed different scores in students perception of development of critical thinking skills ($F=244,661$, $p<0.05$). The higher scores in development of student critical thinking skills during the studies were observed between students who participated in 51-75% of lectures ($m=3.63$) and 76-100% of lectures ($m=3.83$). Students that participated in a less amount of lectures demonstrated lower scores in development of student analytical thinking skills (0-25% attendance of lectures ($m=3.23$), 26-

50% attendance of lectures (m=3.46)). Scheffe test showed that there was significant different between all student groups in terms of development of student critical thinking skills. Tables below show SPSS output of the above statistics.

Table 24. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction different level of lectures attendance and students evaluation of development of critical thinking skills

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>				
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	1218	3,23	1,234	0,035
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	2529	3,46	1,072	0,021
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	10529	3,63	1,057	0,010
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	27858	3,83	1,075	0,006
<i>Total</i>	42134	3,74	1,084	0,005

<i>ANOVA</i>					
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	848,249	3	282,750	244,661	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	48688,846	42130	1,156		
<i>Total</i>	49537,095	42133			

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Lectures attendance</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>-,237*</i>	<i>0,037</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,402*</i>	<i>0,033</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,599*</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,237*</i>	<i>0,037</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,166*</i>	<i>0,024</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,362*</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,402*</i>	<i>0,033</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,166*</i>	<i>0,024</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,197*</i>	<i>0,012</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,599*</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,362*</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>,197*</i>	<i>0,012</i>	<i>0,000</i>

Thus, to summarize the results of ANOVA analysis, it was indicated that all of the 5 aspects regarding different dimension of educational service quality were highly evaluated by students. All of the scores were evaluated above point 3 in Likert five (5) point scale which means that students receive high quality in teaching quality, study content quality and are satisfied with development of critical thinking, analytical thing and abilities of expression of personal opinion during the studies. However, all those 5 aspects (except 'quality perception of course content' in terms of different education level(Bachelor, Master, Integrated studies degree)) -satisfaction with teaching quality, study content quality, critical thinking, analytical thing, expression of personal opinion was evaluated significantly different in terms of different study field, study course, level of education and lectures attendance. In more details, that the highest evaluations in all 5 aspects were observed between students who were studying in Humanitarian and Social science. In terms of level of education, master degree student showed the highest evaluations in critical

thinking, analytical thing, expression of personal opinion. These finding could be perhaps attributed to the fact that master degree studies require higher order skills in analysis, critical thinking and personal knowledge in compare with bachelor studies. In terms of study courses, student from lower study courses (1st , 2nd) showed higher evaluations in all 5 aspects of educational service quality compared to the students from higher courses. It supported previous findings by Melchor and Bravo (2012) that level of satisfaction with the learning experience decrease over time and that further attention should be paid on this variable while modelling students evaluations of educational experience. In terms of level of lecture attendance, also important findings were observed – student satisfaction with teaching quality, study content quality, critical thinking, analytical thinking, expression of personal opinion decreases with lower attendance of lectures. These findings contribute to the findings that students who attend less lectures, are less interacted and involved in the study process and consequently receive less value from the studies. The effect might be valid vice versa (Navarro et al., 2005). All in all, according to the results provided above in the tables, the hypothesis **H1-H4** (except the hypothesis **H2-a: There is a significant effect of type of education level on quality perception of course content that was rejected (p=0.099)**) **were confirmed.** (More tables see in appendix)

Furtherly, in order to broader the analysis, the same one-way ANOVA method for all 5 aspects of perceived educational service quality was implied due to exploration of the second sample of the research (*Sample 2*). The level of attendance was not included in this sample as this item was missing in the questionnaire provided by the university database. The tables below demonstrate the summarized results of ANOVA test of conducted analysis for all 5 aspects of perceived educational service quality in terms of different study field, level of education, course. (See more tables - ‘Descriptives’ and ‘Comparison Table’ in appendix).

Table 25. Comparison of SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field, level of education, study course and quality perception of course content

ANOVA					
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content. (BY Field of Study)</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	56,499	3	18,833	19,887	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10297,797	10874	0,947		
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content. (BY Level of Education)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	10,839	2	5,420	5,670	0,003
<i>Within Groups</i>	10612,827	11104	0,956		
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content. (BY Study Course)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	72,621	5	14,524	15,248	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10394,796	10913	0,953		

Table 26. Comparison of SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field, level of education, study course and perception of teaching quality

ANOVA					
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching (BY Field of Study)</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	102,218	3	34,073	33,929	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10924,930	10879	1,004		
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching (BY Level of Education)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	6,507	2	3,254	3,194	0,041
<i>Within Groups</i>	11316,005	11108	1,019		
<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching (BY Study Course)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	72,823	5	14,565	14,320	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	11102,694	10916	1,017		

Table 27. Comparison of SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field, level of education, study course and encouragement to express student personal opinion during the studies

ANOVA					
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies. (BY Field of Study)</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	535,214	3	178,405	170,948	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10998,736	10539	1,044		
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.(BY Level of Education)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	118,952	2	59,476	54,809	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	11676,174	10760	1,085		
<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies. (BY Study Course)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	59,647	5	11,929	10,899	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	11587,960	10587	1,095		

Table 28. Comparison of SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field, level of education, study course and encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies

ANOVA					
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.(BY Field of Study)</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	194,184	3	64,728	66,344	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10327,212	10585	0,976		
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.(BY Level of Education)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	112,502	2	56,251	57,039	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10657,731	10807	0,986		
<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.(BY Study course)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	30,679	5	6,136	6,160	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	10591,582	10634	0,996		

Table 29. Comparison of SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field, level of education, study course and students evaluation of development of critical thinking skills

ANOVA					
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking (BY Field of Study)</i>					
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	257,930	3	85,977	75,137	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	12013,587	10499	1,144		
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking (BY Level of Education)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	89,261	2	44,631	38,440	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	12446,452	10720	1,161		
<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking (BY Study course)</i>					
<i>Between Groups</i>	46,600	5	9,320	7,991	0,000
<i>Within Groups</i>	12305,207	10551	1,166		

To sum up the results provided, statistical one-way ANOVA analysis using *Sample 2* has showed that all of the other five aspect including in perceived educational service quality – **course content quality perception, teaching quality perception, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills** were significantly different in terms of the different study field, level of education, course and lectures attendance with $p < 0.05$. It confesses with the *Sample 1* results where the analysis of interaction between respondents at different levels (degree) of studies and quality perception of course content showed that there are no significant differences between respondents who studies in Bachelor, Master and Integrated studies degree in terms of perceived quality of courses content ($p=0.99$). Moreover, ANOVA test also showed (see ‘Descriptives’ tables in appendix) the same results as *sample 1* that the highest evaluations in all 5 aspects were observed between students who were studying in Humanitarian and Social science. In terms of level of education, analysis using *sample 2* also indicated that master degree students provides the highest evaluations in critical thinking, analytical thing, expression of personal opinion. Thus, to summarize, according to the results of ANOVA analysis of *sample 2* all of the hypotheses **H1- H4** regarding significant differences in evaluation of course content quality perception, teaching quality perception,

students' encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills in different field of studies, level of education and study course **are confirmed**.

3.2. Differences in students satisfaction and loyalty intentions in different study field, level of education and course

In the theoretical background, it was revealed that such factors as chosen studies field, level of education, course or lectures attendance have impact on students satisfaction (Helgesen and Nettet, 2007). Thus it was assumed that is important to examine their influence in the mix of factors that effect satisfaction rates and correspondingly – student loyalty intention (The annual BC College and Institute Student Outcomes Survey, 2002).

As a second stage of the analysis of this paper, MANOVA analysis was conducted in order to explore the differences between students overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions regarding the different **field of study, level of education** and **study course** and to test **H5 – H7** hypotheses. The analysis was conducted using the *Sample 2* as it fulfilled the requirement for all the variables needed for deeper analysis of the underlying linkage between general satisfaction and student intention to be loyal.

As the initial step, the examination of differences in overall **satisfaction** and **loyalty** scores within various *study fields* – Humanitarian studies, Social studies, Biomedical studies and Physical studies- was implied. The tables below show the results of implemented MANOVA analysis.

Table 30. SPSS outputs of MANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field and students overall satisfaction as well as scores in loyalty intentions

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
<i>Field of Science</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	4,13	0,925
	<i>Social studies</i>	4,05	0,982
	<i>Physical studies</i>	4,00	0,944
	<i>Biomedical studies</i>	3,97	1,015
	<i>Total</i>	4,04	0,969
<i>Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	4,07	1,183
	<i>Social studies</i>	3,93	1,206
	<i>Physical studies</i>	3,89	1,202
	<i>Biomedical studies</i>	3,83	1,299
	<i>Total</i>	3,94	1,222

Multiple Comparisons					
<i>Scheffe</i>					
<i>Dependent Variable</i>			<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	<i>Social studies</i>	,08*	0,025	0,012
		<i>Physical studies</i>	,13*	0,028	0,000
		<i>Biomedical studies</i>	,16*	0,028	0,000
	<i>Social studies</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	-,08*	0,025	0,012
		<i>Physical studies</i>	0,05	0,027	0,306
		<i>Biomedical studies</i>	,08*	0,027	0,029
	<i>Physical studies</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	-,13*	0,028	0,000
		<i>Social studies</i>	-0,05	0,027	0,306
		<i>Biomedical studies</i>	0,03	0,030	0,820
	<i>Biomedical studies</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	-,16*	0,028	0,000
		<i>Social studies</i>	-,08*	0,027	0,029
		<i>Physical studies</i>	-0,03	0,030	0,820
<i>Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	<i>Social studies</i>	,14*	0,031	0,000
		<i>Physical studies</i>	,18*	0,036	0,000
		<i>Biomedical studies</i>	,24*	0,036	0,000
	<i>Social studies</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	-,14*	0,031	0,000
		<i>Physical studies</i>	0,04	0,034	0,623
		<i>Biomedical studies</i>	,10*	0,033	0,032
	<i>Physical studies</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	-,18*	0,036	0,000
		<i>Social studies</i>	-0,04	0,034	0,623
		<i>Biomedical studies</i>	0,05	0,038	0,552
	<i>Biomedical studies</i>	<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	-,24*	0,036	0,000
		<i>Social studies</i>	-,10*	0,033	0,032
		<i>Physical studies</i>	-0,05	0,038	0,552

<i>Multivariate Tests^a</i>						
<i>Effect</i>		<i>Value</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Hypothesis df</i>	<i>Error df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	<i>Pillai's Trace</i>	0,944	87243,162 ^b	2,000	10404,000	0,000
	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	0,056	87243,162 ^b	2,000	10404,000	0,000
	<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	16,771	87243,162 ^b	2,000	10404,000	0,000
	<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	16,771	87243,162 ^b	2,000	10404,000	0,000
<i>FieldofScience</i>	<i>Pillai's Trace</i>	0,005	9,005	6,000	20810,000	0,000
	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	0,995	9,015 ^b	6,000	20808,000	0,000
	<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	0,005	9,025	6,000	20806,000	0,000
	<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	0,005	17,680 ^c	3,000	10405,000	0,000

As the results demonstrates (the tables of Multivariate Test and Multiple Comparisons), there was significant effect of field of study on the students general satisfaction and loyalty intentions with p-value <0.05. In more details, Using Pillai's trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace and Roy's Largest Root provided significant effect of field of study on the above mentioned variables with p<0.05. As the results from MANOVA analysis indicates, students from Humanitarian studies has significantly higher satisfaction scores compared to Physical (mean difference = 0.13) and Biomedical studies (mean difference = 0.16). However, there was no significant difference observed between satisfaction scores between students from Social science and Physical science (p>0.05), thus the hypothesis **H5-a was rejected**. The results confesses with the results from survey conducted by Times Higher Education Journal (2012) which revealed that students from social science studies demonstrated more positive educational experience in higher education institutions in compare students from programmes related to technology, engineering or maths. The dissimilarities were identified as caused by the natural differences in teaching methods, studies content or approach.

In addition, while exploring differences in loyalty intentions between different studies field, it as also observed that Humanitarian studies has significantly higher loyalty scores compared to Physical (mean difference = 0.18) and Biomedical studies (mean difference = 0.24). However, there was no significant difference observed between loyalty scores between students

from Social science and Physical science ($p>0.05$), thus the hypothesis **H5-b** was rejected as well.

The tables below show the homogenous subsets regarding the perception of overall satisfaction and loyalty according to different field of studies.

Table 31. SPSS outputs of MANOVA statistics of interaction between different study field and students overall satisfaction as well as scores in loyalty intentions

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.				
<i>Scheffe^{a,b,c}</i>				
<i>Field of Science</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Subset</i>		
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>
<i>Biomedical studies</i>	2115	3,97		
<i>Physical studies</i>	2066	4,00	4,00	
<i>Social studies</i>	3571		4,05	
<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	2657			4,13
<i>Sig.</i>		0,778	0,331	1,000

Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.				
<i>Scheffe^{a,b,c}</i>				
<i>Field of Science</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Subset</i>		
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>
<i>Biomedical studies</i>	2115	3,83		
<i>Physical studies</i>	2066	3,89	3,89	
<i>Social studies</i>	3571		3,93	
<i>Humanitarian studies</i>	2657			4,07
<i>Sig.</i>		0,477	0,643	1,000

As the second step in the MANOVA analysis, the examination of differences in overall **satisfaction** and **loyalty** scores within various *level of education* – Bachelor studies, Master studies and Integrated studies - was implied. The tables below show the results of implemented MANOVA analysis.

Table 32. SPSS outputs of MANOVA statistics of interaction between different level of studies and students overall satisfaction as well as scores in loyalty intentions

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
<i>Level of Education</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	<i>B</i>	4,05	0,956
	<i>M</i>	3,98	0,978
	<i>Vn</i>	4,04	1,018
	<i>Total</i>	4,04	0,971
<i>Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.</i>	<i>B</i>	3,96	1,203
	<i>M</i>	3,86	1,263
	<i>Vn</i>	3,95	1,248
	<i>Total</i>	3,94	1,220

<i>Multivariate Tests^a</i>						
<i>Effect</i>		<i>Value</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Hypothesis df</i>	<i>Error df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	<i>Pillai's Trace</i>	0,917	58303,299 ^b	2,000	10623,000	0,000
	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	0,083	58303,299 ^b	2,000	10623,000	0,000
	<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	10,977	58303,299 ^b	2,000	10623,000	0,000
	<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	10,977	58303,299 ^b	2,000	10623,000	0,000
<i>StudyDegree</i>	<i>Pillai's Trace</i>	0,001	2,223	4,000	21248,000	0,064
	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	0,999	2,224 ^b	4,000	21246,000	0,064
	<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	0,001	2,224	4,000	21244,000	0,064
	<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	0,001	4,396 ^c	2,000	10624,000	0,012

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>					
<i>Scheffe</i>					
<i>Dependent Variable</i>			<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>,07*</i>	<i>0,028</i>	<i>0,040</i>
		<i>Vn</i>	<i>0,01</i>	<i>0,025</i>	<i>0,844</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>-,07*</i>	<i>0,028</i>	<i>0,040</i>
		<i>Vn</i>	<i>-0,06</i>	<i>0,034</i>	<i>0,235</i>
	<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>-0,01</i>	<i>0,025</i>	<i>0,844</i>
		<i>M</i>	<i>0,06</i>	<i>0,034</i>	<i>0,235</i>
<i>Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>,10*</i>	<i>0,035</i>	<i>0,016</i>
		<i>Vn</i>	<i>0,01</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,926</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>-,10*</i>	<i>0,035</i>	<i>0,016</i>
		<i>Vn</i>	<i>-0,09</i>	<i>0,042</i>	<i>0,107</i>
	<i>Vn</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>-0,01</i>	<i>0,031</i>	<i>0,926</i>
		<i>M</i>	<i>0,09</i>	<i>0,042</i>	<i>0,107</i>

As the results demonstrates (the tables of Multivariate Test), Pillai's trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace do not provided significant effect of level of study on the above mentioned variables with $p < 0.05$. Only Roy's Largest Root showed the significance of level of studies with $p \text{ value} < 0.05$. As the results from MANOVA analysis indicates, students from Master degree studies has significantly lower satisfaction scores compared to Bachelor degree students (mean difference = - 0.7) and lower scores, but not significantly if compared to satisfaction score in Integrated studies ($p > 0.05$). Thus the hypothesis **H6-a was rejected**. The findings confronted with the previous finding by authors Abdul et al. (2004), which revealed that student postgraduates showed more positive perception towards the academic experience. In addition, while exploring differences in loyalty intentions between different level of education, it was observed that Master degree studies has significantly lower loyalty scores compared to Bachelor degree students (mean difference = - 0.1) and lower scores, but not significantly if compared to satisfaction score in Integrated studies ($p > 0.05$). Thus the hypothesis **H6-b was rejected** as well.

The tables below show the homogenous subsets regarding the perception of overall satisfaction and loyalty according to different level of education.

Table 33. SPSS outputs of MANOVA statistics of interaction between different level of education and students overall satisfaction as well as scores in loyalty intentions

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.			
Scheffe ^{a,b,c}			
Level of Education	N	Subset	
		1	2
M	1423	3,98	
Vn	2000	4,04	4,04
B	7204		4,05
Sig.		0,143	0,886

Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.			
Scheffe ^{a,b,c}			
Level of Education	N	Subset	
		1	2
M	1423	3,86	
Vn	2000		3,95
B	7204		3,96
Sig.		1,000	0,947

As the final step in the MANOVA analysis, the examination of differences in overall **satisfaction** and **loyalty** scores within various *course of study* – 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th – was implied. The tables below show the results of implemented MANOVA analysis.

Table 34. SPSS outputs of MANOVA statistics of interaction between different study course and students overall satisfaction as well as scores in loyalty intentions

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
<i>Study Course</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	<i>1 kurasas</i>	4,14	0,948
	<i>2 kurasas</i>	4,02	0,955
	<i>3 kurasas</i>	3,94	0,973
	<i>4 kurasas</i>	3,97	1,002
	<i>5 kurasas</i>	3,68	1,174
	<i>6 kurasas</i>	3,68	0,976
	<i>Total</i>	4,03	0,973
<i>Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.</i>	<i>1 kurasas</i>	4,05	1,189
	<i>2 kurasas</i>	3,93	1,221
	<i>3 kurasas</i>	3,83	1,233
	<i>4 kurasas</i>	3,86	1,231
	<i>5 kurasas</i>	3,51	1,430
	<i>6 kurasas</i>	3,62	1,280
	<i>Total</i>	3,93	1,223

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>					
<i>Scheffe</i>					
<i>Dependent Variable</i>			<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	<i>1 kurasas</i>	<i>2 kurasas</i>	,12*	0,024	0,000
		<i>3 kurasas</i>	,20*	0,025	0,000
		<i>4 kurasas</i>	,17*	0,032	0,000
		<i>5 kurasas</i>	,46*	0,064	0,000
		<i>6 kurasas</i>	0,46	0,167	0,171
	<i>2 kurasas</i>	<i>1 kurasas</i>	-,12*	0,024	0,000
		<i>3 kurasas</i>	0,08	0,027	0,166
		<i>4 kurasas</i>	0,04	0,034	0,887
		<i>5 kurasas</i>	,33*	0,065	0,000
		<i>6 kurasas</i>	0,34	0,167	0,522
	<i>3 kurasas</i>	<i>1 kurasas</i>	-,20*	0,025	0,000
		<i>2 kurasas</i>	-0,08	0,027	0,166
		<i>4 kurasas</i>	-0,03	0,034	0,971
		<i>5 kurasas</i>	,26*	0,065	0,008
		<i>6 kurasas</i>	0,27	0,167	0,774
	<i>4 kurasas</i>	<i>1 kurasas</i>	-,17*	0,032	0,000
		<i>2 kurasas</i>	-0,04	0,034	0,887
		<i>3 kurasas</i>	0,03	0,034	0,971

		5 kurasas	,29*	0,068	0,003	
		6 kurasas	0,30	0,168	0,681	
	5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,46*	0,064	0,000	
		2 kurasas	-,33*	0,065	0,000	
		3 kurasas	-,26*	0,065	0,008	
		4 kurasas	-,29*	0,068	0,003	
		6 kurasas	0,01	0,177	1,000	
	6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-0,46	0,167	0,171	
		2 kurasas	-0,34	0,167	0,522	
		3 kurasas	-0,27	0,167	0,774	
		4 kurasas	-0,30	0,168	0,681	
		5 kurasas	-0,01	0,177	1,000	
<i>Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.</i>	1 kurasas	2 kurasas	,12*	0,031	0,009	
		3 kurasas	,23*	0,031	0,000	
		4 kurasas	,19*	0,040	0,000	
		5 kurasas	,54*	0,080	0,000	
		6 kurasas	0,43	0,210	0,513	
		2 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,12*	0,031	0,009
			3 kurasas	0,10	0,035	0,109
			4 kurasas	0,07	0,043	0,759
			5 kurasas	,42*	0,082	0,000
			6 kurasas	0,31	0,210	0,822
		3 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,23*	0,031	0,000
			2 kurasas	-0,10	0,035	0,109
			4 kurasas	-0,03	0,043	0,986
			5 kurasas	,32*	0,082	0,010
			6 kurasas	0,21	0,210	0,965
		4 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,19*	0,040	0,000
			2 kurasas	-0,07	0,043	0,759
			3 kurasas	0,03	0,043	0,986
			5 kurasas	,35*	0,086	0,005
			6 kurasas	0,24	0,212	0,934
		5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,54*	0,080	0,000
			2 kurasas	-,42*	0,082	0,000
			3 kurasas	-,32*	0,082	0,010
			4 kurasas	-,35*	0,086	0,005
			6 kurasas	-0,11	0,223	0,999
		6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-0,43	0,210	0,513
			2 kurasas	-0,31	0,210	0,822
			3 kurasas	-0,21	0,210	0,965
			4 kurasas	-0,24	0,212	0,934
			5 kurasas	0,11	0,223	0,999

<i>Multivariate Tests^a</i>						
<i>Effect</i>		<i>Value</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Hypothesis df</i>	<i>Error df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	<i>Pillai's Trace</i>	0,616	8374,505 ^b	2,000	10432,000	0,000
	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	0,384	8374,505 ^b	2,000	10432,000	0,000
	<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	1,606	8374,505 ^b	2,000	10432,000	0,000
	<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	1,606	8374,505 ^b	2,000	10432,000	0,000
<i>StudyCourse</i>	<i>Pillai's Trace</i>	0,012	12,193	10,000	20866,000	0,000
	<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	0,988	12,226 ^b	10,000	20864,000	0,000
	<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	0,012	12,259	10,000	20862,000	0,000
	<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	0,012	24,273 ^c	5,000	10433,000	0,000

As the results demonstrates (the tables of Multivariate Test and Multiple Comparisons), there was significant effect of field of study on the students general satisfaction and loyalty intentions with p-value <0.05. In more details, Using Pillai's trace, Wilks' Lambda, Hotelling's Trace and Roy's Largest Root provided significant effect of study course on the above mentioned variables with p<0.05. As the results from MANOVA analysis indicates, students from higher courses (3rd – 6th courses) mainly have lower satisfaction scores compared to students from lower courses (1st -3rd courses). Thus the hypothesis **H7-a was rejected**. The results supported finding by authors Melchor and Bravo (2012) that revealed that level of satisfaction with the learning experience decrease over time. In addition, while exploring differences in loyalty intentions between different level of education, it was observed that students from higher courses (3rd – 6th courses) mainly have lower loyalty scores compared to students from lower courses (1st -3rd courses). Thus the hypothesis **H7-b was rejected**.

The tables below show the homogenous subsets regarding the perception of overall satisfaction and loyalty according to different study courses.

Table 35. SPSS outputs of MANOVA statistics of interaction between different study courses and students overall satisfaction as well as scores in loyalty intentions

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.			
<i>Scheffe^{a,b,c}</i>			
<i>Study Course</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Subset</i>	
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>
6 kurasas	34	3,68	
5 kurasas	244	3,68	
3 kurasas	2411	3,94	3,94
4 kurasas	1186	3,97	3,97
2 kurasas	2557	4,02	4,02
1 kurasas	4007		4,14
<i>Sig.</i>		0,060	0,614

Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.			
<i>Scheffe^{a,b,c}</i>			
<i>Study Course</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Subset</i>	
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>
5 kurasas	244	3,51	
6 kurasas	34	3,62	3,62
3 kurasas	2411	3,83	3,83
4 kurasas	1186	3,86	3,86
2 kurasas	2557	3,93	3,93
1 kurasas	4007		4,05
<i>Sig.</i>		0,072	0,058

Finally, in order to examine the hypothesis **H8** which suggests that students with high level of lectures attendance have higher overall satisfaction scores than low level of lectures attendance the *Sample 1* was used as this data set was provided by the relevant responses regarding the lectures attendance. To explore the differences between different level of lectures attendance in terms of student overall satisfaction, one-way ANOVA analysis was employed. As the results below showed there is a significant difference between different level of lectures attendance in terms of student overall satisfaction ($p < 0.05$). In addition, Scheffe test provided

that students who participated in 51-75% of lectures (m=3.65) and 76-100% of lectures (m=3.96) were significantly more satisfied with the studies compare to the students who participation in lecture were lower with the following results: 0 -25% (m=3.21) and 26-50% (m=3.42). These results contribute to the findings that students who attend less lectures, are less interacted and involved in the study process and consequently receive less value from the studies. The effect might be valid vice versa (Navarro et al., 2005). According to the results, the hypothesis **H8 was confirmed.**

Table 36. SPSS outputs of ANOVA statistics of interaction between different level of lectures attendance and student's overall satisfaction scores

<i>Descriptives</i>				
<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>1230</i>	<i>3,21</i>	<i>1,270</i>	<i>0,036</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>2536</i>	<i>3,43</i>	<i>1,088</i>	<i>0,022</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>10547</i>	<i>3,66</i>	<i>1,012</i>	<i>0,010</i>
<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>27941</i>	<i>3,94</i>	<i>0,983</i>	<i>0,006</i>
<i>Total</i>	<i>42254</i>	<i>3,82</i>	<i>1,024</i>	<i>0,005</i>

<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>				
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>			
<i>Scheffe</i>				
<i>(I) Lectures attendance</i>		<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>-,220[*]</i>	<i>0,035</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,451[*]</i>	<i>0,030</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,733[*]</i>	<i>0,029</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,220[*]</i>	<i>0,035</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>-,231[*]</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>76 - 100 proc.</i>	<i>-,514[*]</i>	<i>0,021</i>	<i>0,000</i>
<i>51 - 75 proc.</i>	<i>0 - 25 proc.</i>	<i>,451[*]</i>	<i>0,030</i>	<i>0,000</i>
	<i>26 - 50 proc.</i>	<i>,231[*]</i>	<i>0,022</i>	<i>0,000</i>

	76 - 100 proc.	-,283 [*]	0,011	0,000
76 - 100 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,733 [*]	0,029	0,000
	26 - 50 proc.	,514 [*]	0,021	0,000
	51 - 75 proc.	,283 [*]	0,011	0,000

3.3. Relationship between perceived educational service quality as well as overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions in higher education sector (Pearson correlation; Multiple regression; Logistic regression analysis; Mediating effects)

According to Taylor (1990) correlation analysis is mainly used to identify the strength and direction of linear relationship between two variables. As the next initial step, before implementing regression analysis, the strength of correlation between each element of perceived educational service quality and overall student satisfaction which was analysed (using the *Sample 2*) as a separate variable from the above analysed 5 items related with education service quality, as well as loyalty intentions. The Pearson coefficient R has its values in the interval [-1;1] and could indicate the direction of relationship between two continuous variables.

Table 37. Pearson correlation table of different elements of perceived high education quality with student overall satisfaction

		Course content quality perception	Teaching quality perception	Encouragement to express personal opinion	Development of analytical	Development of critical thinking skills
Student overall satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.728**	.690**	.526**	.510**	.538**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

	N	11107	11107	11107	11107	11107
Student loyalty	Pearson Correlation	.599**	.577**	.489**	.483**	.517**
	Sig. (2- tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	11107	11107	11107	11107	11107
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)						

As the Table 8 shows, Bivariate Correlation indicates statistically significant correlation between perceived educational service quality, students overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions with p value <0.05. In more details, as Bivariate Correlation demonstrates, Pearson Correlation values are positive and above 0.5 therefore there is a positive relationship between elements of perceived service quality, student overall satisfaction and loyalty. In addition, it showed that the highest correlation is between content, teaching quality and overall satisfaction. Results support findings by authors Douglas et al. (2006), which revealed that the most important aspects leading student satisfaction are lectures content and positive education experience with the teachers. However, as Pearson Correlation can only identify weather it is correlation and its strength, further analysis as multiple regression and logistic regression would be implemented for more detailed results.

Thus, consequently, *multiple regression analysis* was performed using the data from *Sample 2* in order to explore if there is a positive impact of various elements of student perceived educational service quality such as quality of courses content, teaching, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills as well as overall student satisfaction on loyalty and to test hypothesis **H9-H11**. Student loyalty was employed as the dependent variable, while others variables were classified as independent variables.

As the initial step, the multicollinearity was checked in order to satisfy the key assumptions of selected statistical analysis. After conducting Pearson's correlations all of the results were positive. Moreover, no multicollinearity was observed as all VIF levels were < 4 . Furtherly, the model fit was identified a relevant fit as well as R^2 were > 0.20 and Anova $p < 0.05$.

Table 38. Summary of multiple regression analysis

<i>Model Summary^b</i>					
<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>Adjusted R Square</i>	<i>Std. Error of the Estimate</i>	<i>Durbin-Watson</i>
1	,726 ^a	0,528	0,527	0,836	1,968

<i>ANOVA^a</i>						
<i>Model</i>		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
1	<i>Regression</i>	7904,748	6	1317,458	1883,195	,000 ^b
	<i>Residual</i>	7074,221	10112	0,700		
	<i>Total</i>	14978,969	10118			

<i>Coefficients^a</i>						
<i>Model</i>				<i>Standardized Coefficients</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
				<i>Beta</i>		
1	(Constant)	-	0,041		-1,952	0,051
		0,079				
	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>	0,121	0,015	0,097	7,964	0,000
	<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching</i>	0,083	0,014	0,069	5,905	0,000
	<i>Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.</i>	0,033	0,013	0,028	2,491	0,013
	<i>Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.</i>	0,042	0,015	0,034	2,752	0,006
	<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking</i>	0,127	0,014	0,112	9,116	0,000
	<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	0,610	0,014	0,486	44,933	0,000

According to the analysis, it was reveal that selected independent variables could explain quite high amount of the variance in “student loyalty intentions” – 53%. In addition, according the Coefficients table it could be observed that there are positive relationship between all of the 6 independent variables (perception of quality of courses content and teaching, encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills as well as overall student satisfaction) and student intentions to be loyal to their educational institution. Beta

coefficients also indicates that the most important variable in the linear regression is student's overall satisfaction ($B=0.610$) while the other ones are much less important factors. The results supported previous findings by Helgessen and Nettet (2007) which stated in their study that satisfaction is perceived as a key and the most important factor explaining student loyalty. In addition, it could be also observed that other important (but less) factors are development of critical thinking, quality of course content and quality of teaching. All in all, according the regression results, it could be seen that hypothesis **H10 - H11** could be **confirmed**.

Logistic regression. Furtherly, logistic regression was conducted using the data from *Sample I* (with dichotomous variables reflecting student loyalty intentions) in order to broader the analyse above and to explore if there is a positive relationship between various elements of student perceived educational service quality such as quality of courses content, teaching, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills as well as overall student satisfaction and loyalty. The hypothesis **H10 and H11** were tested. The tables below show the summary of logistic regression analysis.

Table 39. Classification Table and Omnibus Test of logistic regression analysis

<i>Classification Table^a</i>					
	<i>Observed</i>				
<i>Step 1</i>	<i>Item 7. I will refer this study programme to my friends/family.</i>	<i>Ne</i>	3859	5466	41,4
		<i>Taip</i>	1295	28662	95,7
	<i>Overall Percentage</i>				82,8

<i>Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients</i>				
		<i>Chi-square</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Step 1</i>	<i>Step</i>	12354,222	8	0,000
	<i>Block</i>	12354,222	8	0,000
	<i>Model</i>	12354,222	8	0,000

According to the results above, Classification Table presented that 41,4 % of students who are not willing to refer their study programme and 95,7% of students who are willing to refer their study programme were classified correctly using this logistic regression analysis. Moreover, Omnibus Test showed all p values significant (<0.05).

Table 40. Model summary of logistic regression analysis

Model Summary			
Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	30702,632 ^a	0,270	0,405

Moreover, Nagelkerke pseudo-coefficient presented with quite high value 0.405 which is > 0.20. However, the table ‘Variables in Education’ below presented that not all of the variables included in the logistic regression are statistically significant. Item 3 and Item 4 were not significant variables in the logistic regression, thus hypothesis **H11-c** and **H11-d** were rejected. Although, hypothesis **H10**, **H11-a**, **H11-b** and **H11-e** were proved.

Table 41. Variables in the Equation of logistic regression analysis

Variables in the Equation						
		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.
Step 1 ^a	Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.	0,249	0,023	115,690	1	0,000
	Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.	0,140	0,023	37,663	1	0,000
	Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.	0,027	0,020	1,775	1	0,183
	Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.	-0,032	0,022	2,120	1	0,145
	Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.	0,162	0,020	66,623	1	0,000
	Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.	1,025	0,024	1892,280	1	0,000
	Level of education			14,791	2	0,001
	Level of education (1)	-0,101	0,037	7,437	1	0,006
	Level of education (2)	-0,196	0,052	14,237	1	0,000
	Constant	-4,315	0,076	3217,441	1	0,000

Thus, according to those results further logistic analysis was conducted by eliminating not significant above mentioned variables – encouragement of expression personal student opinion and development of analytical skills. Consequently, the following results were presented:

Table 42. Summary of logistic regression analysis

Classification Table^a					
<i>Observed</i>					
<i>Step 1</i>	<i>Item 7. I will refer this study programme to my friends/family.</i>	<i>Ne</i>	3862	5476	41,4
		<i>Taip</i>	1303	28700	95,7
	<i>Overall Percentage</i>				82,8

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients				
		<i>Chi-square</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Step 1</i>	<i>Step</i>	127371,342	6	0,000
	<i>Block</i>	127371,342	6	0,000
	<i>Model</i>	127371,342	6	0,000

Model Summary			
<i>Step</i>	<i>-2 Log likelihood</i>	<i>Cox & Snell R Square</i>	<i>Nagelkerke R Square</i>
1	30747,834 ^a	0,270	0,405

Variables in the Equation						
		<i>B</i>	<i>S.E.</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
<i>Step 1^a</i>	<i>Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.</i>	0,251	0,023	119,191	1	0,000
	<i>Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.</i>	0,141	0,023	38,459	1	0,000
	<i>Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.</i>	0,156	0,016	94,884	1	0,000
	<i>Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.</i>	1,025	0,024	1902,687	1	0,000
	<i>Level of education</i>			14,883	2	0,001
	<i>Level of education (1)</i>	-0,101	0,037	7,461	1	0,006
	<i>Level of education (2)</i>	-0,194	0,051	14,307	1	0,000
	<i>Constant</i>	-4,325	0,072	3630,910	1	0,000

According to those results it could be observed that after elimination Item3 and Item4, all the variables in the logistic regression are significant with $p < 0.05$, in line with high Nagelkerke pseudo-coefficient value 0.405 which is > 0.20 and significant Omnibus Test results with $p < 0.05$. It supports previous results from linear regression which indicated the same educational service quality variables – overall satisfaction, development of critical thinking, quality of course content and quality of teaching as the most important ones. The results supported previous findings by Helgessen and Nettet (2007) which stated in their study that satisfaction is perceived as a key and the most important factor explaining student loyalty

Mediation. Further the effect of overall student satisfaction as a mediator between different aspects of perceived educational service quality and loyalty intentions is tested. According to the recent students, it is suggested that overall student satisfaction can be a mediating variable between the perceived educational service quality and loyalty intentions. In other words, satisfaction could have direct and indirect impact on student loyalty intentions (Annamdevula et al., 2014). Other author Lam et al. (2004) also supported those finding claiming that perceived education service quality has a key impact on student satisfaction and loyalty. Hence, **H12** hypothesis is formulated suggesting that various elements of educational service quality have indirect (towards overall satisfaction) and direct impact on students loyalty.

The results of linear regression are presented in the table below and it could be observed that 5 previously explored educational service items are significant at 0.000 in terms of student loyalty. All standardized regression coefficients vary between 0.586 and 0.698 which means that they have strong positive relationship on student intention to be loyal.

Table 43. Coefficients in linear regression analysis

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
1	(Constant)	1,084	0,038		28,330	0,000		
	Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.	0,749	0,010	0,599	77,122	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
		Beta				Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	1,327	0,037		35,652	0,000		
	Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching	0,698	0,010	0,577	72,736	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
		Beta				Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	1,724	0,040		42,721	0,000		
	Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.	0,570	0,010	0,489	57,041	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
		Beta				Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	1,589	0,043		36,732	0,000		
	Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.	0,590	0,011	0,483	56,174	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
		Beta				Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	1,698	0,038		44,551	0,000		
	Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking	0,586	0,010	0,517	61,270	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

According to the results of linear analysis below, the hypotheses **H11 were confirmed** as previously. Furtherly, in order to test the moderation effect of overall satisfaction, the direct positive relation of all elements of perceived educational service quality on overall satisfaction should be proved. In order to examine this relation, linear regression is employed. The results

below demonstrated that all 5 educational service items are significant at 0.000 in terms of student overall satisfaction. All standardized regression coefficients vary between 0.483 and 0.722 which means that they have strong positive relationship on student overall satisfaction with studies.

Table 44. Coefficients in linear regression analysis

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
				Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1,285	0,025		50,700	0,000		
	Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.	0,722	0,006	0,728	111,800	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
				Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1,555	0,026		60,803	0,000		
	Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching	0,663	0,007	0,690	100,293	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
				Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2,141	0,031		69,731	0,000		
	Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.	0,487	0,008	0,526	63,915	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
				Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2,063	0,033		62,261	0,000		
	Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.	0,495	0,008	0,510	61,404	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		Beta					Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2,186	0,029		75,050	0,000		
	Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking	0,483	0,007	0,538	65,934	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

According to the results of linear analysis below, the hypotheses **H9 were confirmed** as well with $p < 0.05$. In addition, as it was previously in this paper examined, student overall satisfaction in studies has strong positive impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions (Hypothesis **H10 were confirmed**). Thus, to test possible mediation effect, the steps developed by Baron and Kenny (1986) were employed. In order to fulfil all first 3 steps, hypothesis **H9 – H11 should be confirmed** as it was applied in this paper during the linear analysis and all those three hypotheses were proved. Finally, to identify if overall satisfaction mediates the relationship between the elements of perceived educational service quality and student loyalty, the direct relationship between elements of perceived educational service quality (independent variable) and student loyalty intention (dependent variable) should be reduced in case of partial mediation or should be reduced to zero in case of full mediation after including mediator (overall satisfaction) in the linear regression. The tables below demonstrate the results of linear analysis.

Table 45. Results of linear regression analysis

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		Beta					Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1,084	0,038		28,330	0,000		
	Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.	0,749	0,010	0,599	77,122	0,000	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients ^a								
Model				Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
				Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0,193	0,037		5,181	0,000		
	Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.	0,238	0,013	0,191	18,980	0,000	0,463	2,159
	Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.	0,703	0,013	0,559	55,673	0,000	0,463	2,159

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

The direct effect of perceived quality of course content on student loyalty intentions reduced (from B=0.749 to B=0.238), but remained significant after including overall satisfaction into the linear regression. The results indicated partial mediation of overall satisfaction between student's perception of quality of course content and student loyalty intentions. Furtherly, the same process and steps to test mediation effect of student overall satisfaction between **teaching quality perception, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills** and students intentions to be loyal were applied. All the results indicated partial mediation of student overall satisfaction as the direct effect of all element of perceived quality of educational service reduced on student loyalty after including overall satisfaction variable in the linear regression.(See the tables in appendix). Thus, according to the results, hypothesis **H12 is confirmed**. The results supported Annamdevula et al., (2014) findings that satisfaction could have direct and indirect impact on student loyalty intentions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Scientific literature provided the following conclusions:

- The analysis of scientific literature revealed that student loyalty towards the higher education institutions are becoming increasingly businesslike and that leads to take student loyalty into important consideration and strategic subject for universities and colleges. Also, the previous researches indicated that students loyalty could be perceived both as behavioural repeatedly approach – taking another degrees at the same educational institutions, usage of university supplementary services, such as the library, catering or IT services, and attitudinal - as intention to continue further studies (other degrees) at the same institution, as well as the willingness to recommend the institution to other persons. Despite the fact that student behavioural loyalty is more measurable, attitudinal loyalty could be also very important as post-graduation attitudinal loyalty might reflect not only as spreading a good word-of mouth, but also as providing financial contributions and job offers to graduated students at the particular academic institution.
- The investigation of the previous researches indicated that although there are many factors contributing to student loyalty, satisfaction and student perception of education service quality are the most important ones. In more details, the attribute of student satisfaction is associated by scholars not only with particular goods or services, but also with broaden aspects of company – personnel interactions or physical facilities. The concept of perceived educational service quality is perceived as multidimensional and as consisting of various aspects such as perception of general content of service, staff, facilities, gained value. In more details, the authors claimed that service quality covers not only the functional performance of service, but also customer emotional, personal benefits that are gained from the particular service and while assessing the quality of service. However, generally, perceived service quality is explained as the level of fulfilment of customer needs in compare with expectations for service performance. In terms of educational service quality, the key variables explaining this concept are course content quality, lectures maintenance and teaching quality.
- The investigation of scientific literature related to quality of educational service and satisfaction impact on student loyalty revealed that satisfaction could play a mediating

role in the relationship between perceived educational service quality and loyalty intentions. In other words, authors claimed that satisfaction could have direct and indirect impact on student loyalty intentions.

- The analysis of the previous researches indicated that perception of educational service quality and general satisfaction may vary depending on student study field, level of education, course and interaction in the lectures generally. The authors claimed that level of satisfaction with the learning experience decrease over time. In terms of level of lecture attendance it was claimed that students who attend less lectures, are less interacted and involved in the study process and consequently could receive less value from the studies. The effect might be valid by contraries. In terms of student level of education, it was proved that which revealed that higher educational level students - postgraduates – have more positive perception towards the receivable academic experience. Also, field of studies have significant impact on students perception of various aspect of educational service. The authors indicated that students from social science studies show more positive educational experience in higher education institutions in compare students from programmes related to technology, engineering or maths. The dissimilarities were identified as caused by the natural differences in teaching methods, studies content or approach.

The analysis of the research provided the following conclusions:

- Following the first research question, perception of course quality content, teaching quality, students' encouragement to express their personal opinion during the studies, development of analytical skills (encouragement to analyse and solve various academic tasks by oneself during the studies) and critical thinking skills as well as in satisfaction and loyalty intentions vary between different study field (Physical, Biomedical, Social, Humanitarian science), level of education (Bachelor, Master, Integrated degree students) ,course (1st -6th) and lectures attendance (0-25%, 26-50%, 51%-75% and 76%-100%). In more details, students from social and humanitarian studies showed higher overall satisfaction, loyalty scores as well as higher scores in perception of course content quality, teaching quality, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills compared to students from physical

and biomedical studies. The finding confirmed previous researches stating that humanitarian and social science students have more positive perception toward the educational experience due to natural differences in study content or learning process. Also, bachelor students are more satisfied and have higher intentions to be loyal than master or integrated studies students towards higher education institution. However, in terms of perception of different elements of educational service such as critical, analytical thinking skills or personal opinion escalation, master degree students showed higher scores. It contributed to the general academic frames that master programme is dedicated more in demonstrating student analytical and critical thinking skills. In terms of study courses, lower course students show higher overall satisfaction and loyalty scores than higher course students and it also contributed to some previous finding which indicated decrease in positive experience of learning process over time. However, it could be related with student lower interaction with studies over time or expectations mismatch with the educational service. Finally, following the first research question, students with high level of lectures attendance have higher satisfaction and loyalty scores as well as higher scores in perception of course content quality, teaching quality, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills compared to those students who level of lectures attendance were lower. The findings were also contributed to the previous researched that indicated students lower interaction and involvement impact on perception of educational experience.

- Following the second research question, the most important factor influencing student loyalty in higher education institutions is overall satisfaction (it explains 49% of loyalty variance). Elements of perceived service quality have lower importance for students loyalty intentions. However, including all of our explored perceived educational service quality variables in line with overall satisfaction, this model could explain more student loyalty variance 52%. The highest impact from elements of educational service quality have teaching quality, critical thinking skills development and course content quality variables. The finding also contributed to the previous researches where it was revealed that loyalty is mostly explained by general satisfaction level with studies in line with course content and teaching quality.
- Following the third research question, students overall satisfaction has a mediating effect on the relation between perceived educational service quality aspects and student

intention to be loyal to the higher education institution. The research results contributed to the previous finding described in the literature analysis where it was assumed that satisfaction could play a mediating role in the relationship between perceived educational service quality and loyalty intentions. In other words, it was proved that satisfaction has direct and indirect impact on student loyalty intentions.

Recommendations:

- The research findings provide a deeper understanding of factors contributing to student intentions to be loyal toward the higher education sector. As the results demonstrate, better student loyalty could be achieved by improving the most important aspects during the studies such as course content and teaching quality as well as critical thinking skills development. Moreover, as it was assumed in the research, students with high level of lectures attendance (51%-75% and 76-100%) have higher satisfaction and loyalty scores as well as higher scores in perception of course content quality, teaching quality, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking skills compared to those students who level of lectures attendance were lower (0-25% or 26-50%). Thus it could be suggested that the level of lectures attendance is an important factor explaining student satisfaction with studies as well as loyalty intentions. In other words, as Navarro et al. (2005) identified in the previous research, perceived quality of educational service may vary depending on the type or length of courses stating that in a short period, different aspects of educational service could be less relevant or student might be less interacted with service, thus they could be less valued as well. In such case, it could be recommended to increase students level of lectures attendance so that the students interaction and involvement into the studies process could be enhanced leading better satisfaction and loyalty scores. The same relation could be valid vice versa.
- According to the results, the most important factor leading in student loyalty is overall satisfaction. In addition, the most important aspects of the educational service quality were associated with the course content, teaching quality and critical thinking skills which leading students satisfaction and loyalty intentions. Thus, in order to increase student satisfaction with studies, those key elements of academic service performance

should be delivered at the most suitable standards. Moreover, as important findings on slight decrease of student positive perception of educational service experience over the time in some aspects were observed, should receive more attention and it could be a great suggestion for further researches to include this variable while analysis students satisfaction and loyalty intentions. In addition, student satisfaction and perception of educational service quality should be monitored consistently over the time and finding should be adapted to the offering service.

Limitations of this work. The database of university semi-annual questionnaires did not provide students demographic data. Moreover, the investigation in this paper was limited only by the information that was lawfully provided. This means that actual students loyal behaviour (taking for another degree in the higher education institution or drop out of the studies) could not be compared with particular student satisfaction or perceived quality scores. In addition, student surveys were covered only by the period from 2014 to 2016 academic year. Finally, other construct included into the analysis such as trust in the university or commitment could be useful to explain and examine student loyalty intentions or behaviour more deeply.

Perceived service quality and satisfaction impact on student loyalty in higher education institutions

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SUMMARY

101 pages, 45 tables, 71 references

The main purpose of this master thesis is to evaluate the impact of various perceived educational service quality elements on overall student satisfaction and loyalty in higher education institutions as well as analyse the impact level of education, study course, lecture attendance and field of study on students loyalty and satisfaction scores.

This master paper consists of three main parts: theoretical background, methodology of the research and data analysis results. The first part of master thesis is dedicated for the academic literature regarding the customer loyalty and its antecedents as well as specifying the literature analysis in terms of student loyalty and factors influencing this concept in higher education sector, furtherly. In more details, in the literature background it was revealed that higher education institutions are becoming increasingly businesslike and that leads to take student loyalty into important consideration and strategic subject for universities and colleges. (Helgesen

& Nettet, 2009). The number of that kind institutions are rapidly growing, thus it results in higher competition and noticeable decline of enrolled students. In such marketplace, it is very important to find the proper ways how to attract and retain students with sufficient academic performance and at the same time to be able to accomplish desirable benchmark of student enrollment as it leads to run higher education institutions operations properly. In other words, it is assumed that for any academic service it is crucial to discover and measure how different aspects and areas contribute to student loyalty in order to enhance both repurchase of the service and spread of positive word-of-mouth or recommendations. Moreover, consistent monitoring and development of the key contributing factors in loyalty improve general image and increase profits of the organization. (Helgesen, 2007; Austin, 2017). In addition to that, sustainable and profitable relationship between customers (students) and the service provider in today's competitive and global market is one of the most challenging areas (Chuah, 2017). Thus, it was concluded that a better understanding of factors influencing students loyalty should be examined. Evaluation of the the impact of various perceived educational service quality elements on overall student satisfaction and loyalty in higher education institutions as well as the deeper analysis of the impact level of education, study course, lecture attendance and field of study on students loyalty and satisfaction scores could contribute to explanation of student's loyalty intentions toward the higher education institution.

In the second part proposed research model, hypothesis, data collection methods and instruments will be presented and discussed. According to the literature, 12 hypotheses were developed. So that the hypothesis would be tested and the aim of this paper will be implemented, the following data were used: *University semi-annually survey data from January of 2012 year till June of 2016 year* (total sample size consists of 43691 observations.(Sample 1)) ;*University semi-annually survey data from June of 2016 year till January of 2017 year* (total sample size consists of 11414 observations.(Sample 2))

In the third part of master thesis the results of data analysis were presented. It was revealed that there are significant differences in perception of various elements of educational service quality as well as in satisfaction and loyalty intentions between different study field, level of education, course and lectures attendance. Moreover, it was identified that the most important factor influencing student loyalty in higher education institutions is overall satisfaction. Other two factors (less, but also important) are critical thinking skills development and course content

quality. Thus, overall satisfaction is an important input to students' intention to be loyal and explains 49% of its variance. However, after including all of our explored perceived educational service quality variables in line with overall satisfaction, this model could explain 52% of student loyalty variance. Finally, it was proved that the students' overall satisfaction has a mediating effect on the relation between perceived educational service quality aspects and student intention to be loyal to the higher education institution.

APPENDIX

3.1 Educational service quality perception in different study field, level of education and course (ANOVA analysis)

- ANOVA tests outputs of interactions between various aspect including in perceived educational service quality –course content quality perception, teaching quality perception, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking in terms of the different study field, level of education, course and lectures attendance (*Sample 1*)

ANOVA

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	241,340	3	80,447	77,130	,000
Within Groups	44067,029	42250	1,043		
Total	44308,369	42253			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

Scheffe

(I) Studies Field Classification	(J) Studies Field Classification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,110*	,012	,000	,08	,14
	"Physical Studies"	,190*	,015	,000	,15	,23
	"Biomedical Studies"	,199*	,016	,000	,15	,24
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,110*	,012	,000	-,14	-,08
	"Physical Studies"	,080*	,014	,000	,04	,12
	"Biomedical Studies"	,088*	,015	,000	,05	,13
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,190*	,015	,000	-,23	-,15
	"Social Studies"	-,080*	,014	,000	-,12	-,04
	"Biomedical Studies"	,009	,018	,972	-,04	,06
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,199*	,016	,000	-,24	-,15
	"Social Studies"	-,088*	,015	,000	-,13	-,05
	"Physical Studies"	-,009	,018	,972	-,06	,04

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

ANOVA

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4,842	2	2,421	2,309	,099
Within Groups	44133,737	42098	1,048		
Total	44138,579	42100			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

Scheffe

(I) Level of education	(J) Level of education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	,023	,015	,319	-,01	,06
	Vn	-,015	,013	,488	-,05	,02
M	B	-,023	,015	,319	-,06	,01
	Vn	-,038	,018	,099	-,08	,01
Vn	B	,015	,013	,488	-,02	,05
	M	,038	,018	,099	-,01	,08

ANOVA

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	787,323	5	157,465	152,859	,000
Within Groups	43521,046	42248	1,030		
Total	44308,369	42253			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 course	2 course	,143 [*]	,014	,000	,10	,19
	3 course	,281 [*]	,014	,000	,23	,33
	4 course	,276 [*]	,014	,000	,23	,32
	5 course	,196 [*]	,024	,000	,12	,28
	6 course	,686 [*]	,035	,000	,57	,80
2 course	1 course	-,143 [*]	,014	,000	-,19	-,10
	3 course	,138 [*]	,015	,000	,09	,19
	4 course	,133 [*]	,015	,000	,08	,18
	5 course	,053	,024	,443	-,03	,13
	6 course	,543 [*]	,036	,000	,42	,66
3 course	1 course	-,281 [*]	,014	,000	-,33	-,23
	2 course	-,138 [*]	,015	,000	-,19	-,09
	4 course	-,005	,016	1,000	-,06	,05
	5 course	-,085 [*]	,025	,035	-,17	,00
	6 course	,405 [*]	,036	,000	,29	,52

3 course	1 course	-,281*	,014	,000	-,33	-,23
	2 course	-,138*	,015	,000	-,19	-,09
	4 course	-,005	,016	1,000	-,06	,05
	5 course	-,085*	,025	,035	-,17	,00
	6 course	,405*	,036	,000	,29	,52
4 course	1 course	-,276*	,014	,000	-,32	-,23
	2 course	-,133*	,015	,000	-,18	-,08
	3 course	,005	,016	1,000	-,05	,06
	5 course	-,080	,025	,060	-,16	,00
	6 course	,410*	,036	,000	,29	,53
5 course	1 course	-,196*	,024	,000	-,28	-,12
	2 course	-,053	,024	,443	-,13	,03
	3 course	,085*	,025	,035	,00	,17
	4 course	,080	,025	,060	,00	,16
	6 course	,490*	,041	,000	,35	,63
6 course	1 course	-,686*	,035	,000	-,80	-,57
	2 course	-,543*	,036	,000	-,66	-,42
	3 course	-,405*	,036	,000	-,52	-,29
	4 course	-,410*	,036	,000	-,53	-,29
	5 course	-,490*	,041	,000	-,63	-,35

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

ANOVA

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1536,684	3	512,228	505,980	,000
Within Groups	42771,685	42250	1,012		
Total	44308,369	42253			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

Scheffe

(I) Lectures attendance	(J) Lectures attendance	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0 - 25 proc.	26 - 50 proc.	-,220*	,035	,000	-,32	-,12
	51 - 75 proc.	-,451*	,030	,000	-,54	-,37
	76 - 100 proc.	-,733*	,029	,000	-,82	-,65
26 - 50 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,220*	,035	,000	,12	,32
	51 - 75 proc.	-,231*	,022	,000	-,29	-,17
	76 - 100 proc.	-,514*	,021	,000	-,57	-,46
51 - 75 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,451*	,030	,000	,37	,54
	26 - 50 proc.	,231*	,022	,000	,17	,29
	76 - 100 proc.	-,283*	,011	,000	-,31	-,25
76 - 100 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,733*	,029	,000	,65	,82
	26 - 50 proc.	,514*	,021	,000	,46	,57
	51 - 75 proc.	,283*	,011	,000	,25	,31

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
"Humanitarian Studies"	12068	3,86	,986	,009	3,85	3,88	1	5
"Social Studies"	16563	3,74	1,022	,008	3,72	3,75	1	5
"Physical Studies"	7546	3,61	1,009	,012	3,59	3,63	1	5
"Biomedical Studies"	6074	3,54	1,076	,014	3,52	3,57	1	5
Total	42251	3,72	1,024	,005	3,71	3,73	1	5

ANOVA

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	528,299	3	176,100	169,983	,000
Within Groups	43767,128	42247	1,036		
Total	44295,427	42250			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

Scheffe

(I) Studies Field Classification	(J) Studies Field Classification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,127 [*]	,012	,000	,09	,16
	"Physical Studies"	,252 [*]	,015	,000	,21	,29
	"Biomedical Studies"	,319 [*]	,016	,000	,27	,36
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,127 [*]	,012	,000	-,16	-,09
	"Physical Studies"	,125 [*]	,014	,000	,09	,16
	"Biomedical Studies"	,191 [*]	,015	,000	,15	,23
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,252 [*]	,015	,000	-,29	-,21
	"Social Studies"	-,125 [*]	,014	,000	-,16	-,09
	"Biomedical Studies"	,067 [*]	,018	,002	,02	,12
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,319 [*]	,016	,000	-,36	-,27
	"Social Studies"	-,191 [*]	,015	,000	-,23	-,15
	"Physical Studies"	-,067 [*]	,018	,002	-,12	-,02

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	27861	3,74	1,000	,006	3,73	3,75	1	5
M	5511	3,73	1,044	,014	3,71	3,76	1	5
Vn	8726	3,66	1,082	,012	3,64	3,68	1	5
Total	42098	3,72	1,024	,005	3,71	3,73	1	5

ANOVA

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	40,984	2	20,492	19,567	,000
Within Groups	44084,870	42095	1,047		
Total	44125,854	42097			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

Scheffe

(I) Level of education	(J) Level of education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	,005	,015	,952	-,03	,04
	Vn	,078*	,013	,000	,05	,11
M	B	-,005	,015	,952	-,04	,03
	Vn	,073*	,018	,000	,03	,12
Vn	B	-,078*	,013	,000	-,11	-,05
	M	-,073*	,018	,000	-,12	-,03

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
0 - 25 proc.	1225	3,20	1,239	,035	3,13	3,27	1	5
26 - 50 proc.	2535	3,41	1,064	,021	3,37	3,45	1	5
51 - 75 proc.	10544	3,57	1,014	,010	3,55	3,59	1	5
76 - 100 proc.	27947	3,83	,993	,006	3,82	3,84	1	5
Total	42251	3,72	1,024	,005	3,71	3,73	1	5

ANOVA

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1145,406	3	381,802	373,812	,000
Within Groups	43150,021	42247	1,021		
Total	44295,427	42250			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching.

Scheffe

(I) Lectures attendance	(J) Lectures attendance	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0 - 25 proc.	26 - 50 proc.	-,206 [*]	,035	,000	-,30	-,11
	51 - 75 proc.	-,372 [*]	,031	,000	-,46	-,29
	76 - 100 proc.	-,629 [*]	,030	,000	-,71	-,55
26 - 50 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,206 [*]	,035	,000	,11	,30
	51 - 75 proc.	-,166 [*]	,022	,000	-,23	-,10
	76 - 100 proc.	-,423 [*]	,021	,000	-,48	-,36
51 - 75 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,372 [*]	,031	,000	,29	,46
	26 - 50 proc.	,166 [*]	,022	,000	,10	,23
	76 - 100 proc.	-,257 [*]	,012	,000	-,29	-,23
76 - 100 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,629 [*]	,030	,000	,55	,71
	26 - 50 proc.	,423 [*]	,021	,000	,36	,48
	51 - 75 proc.	,257 [*]	,012	,000	,23	,29

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
"Humanitarian Studies"	12062	4,12	,941	,009	4,10	4,14	1	5
"Social Studies"	16547	3,92	,992	,008	3,91	3,94	1	5
"Physical Studies"	7516	3,54	1,051	,012	3,51	3,56	1	5
"Biomedical Studies"	6056	3,56	1,119	,014	3,53	3,59	1	5
Total	42181	3,86	1,033	,005	3,85	3,87	1	5

ANOVA

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2218,962	3	739,654	728,357	,000
Within Groups	42831,150	42177	1,016		
Total	45050,112	42180			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Studies Field Classification	(J) Studies Field Classification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,200 [*]	,012	,000	,17	,23
	"Physical Studies"	,585 [*]	,015	,000	,54	,63
	"Biomedical Studies"	,562 [*]	,016	,000	,52	,61
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,200 [*]	,012	,000	-,23	-,17
	"Physical Studies"	,385 [*]	,014	,000	,35	,42
	"Biomedical Studies"	,362 [*]	,015	,000	,32	,40
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,585 [*]	,015	,000	-,63	-,54
	"Social Studies"	-,385 [*]	,014	,000	-,42	-,35
	"Biomedical Studies"	-,023	,017	,625	-,07	,03
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,562 [*]	,016	,000	-,61	-,52
	"Social Studies"	-,362 [*]	,015	,000	-,40	-,32
	"Physical Studies"	,023	,017	,625	-,03	,07

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	27810	3,87	1,016	,006	3,86	3,88	1	5
M	5510	4,09	,956	,013	4,07	4,12	1	5
Vn	8708	3,68	1,101	,012	3,65	3,70	1	5
Total	42028	3,86	1,033	,005	3,85	3,87	1	5

ANOVA

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	597,456	2	298,728	283,539	,000
Within Groups	44276,258	42025	1,054		
Total	44873,714	42027			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Level of education	(J) Level of education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,226*	,015	,000	-,26	-,19
	Vn	,192*	,013	,000	,16	,22
M	B	,226*	,015	,000	,19	,26
	Vn	,418*	,018	,000	,37	,46
Vn	B	-,192*	,013	,000	-,22	-,16
	M	-,418*	,018	,000	-,46	-,37

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 course	11900	3,92	1,009	,009	3,90	3,94	1	5
2 course	10446	3,88	1,034	,010	3,86	3,90	1	5
3 course	8463	3,79	1,023	,011	3,77	3,82	1	5
4 course	8367	3,84	1,047	,011	3,81	3,86	1	5
5 course	2123	3,88	1,046	,023	3,84	3,92	1	5
6 course	882	3,48	1,162	,039	3,41	3,56	1	5
Total	42181	3,86	1,033	,005	3,85	3,87	1	5

ANOVA

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	217,646	5	43,529	40,949	,000
Within Groups	44832,467	42175	1,063		
Total	45050,112	42180			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval Lower Bound	95% Confidence Interval Upper Bound
1 course	2 course	,042	,014	,101	,00	,09
	3 course	,128 [*]	,015	,000	,08	,18
	4 course	,086 [*]	,015	,000	,04	,14
	5 course	,042	,024	,707	-,04	,12
	6 course	,439 [*]	,036	,000	,32	,56
2 course	1 course	-,042	,014	,101	-,09	,00
	3 course	,086 [*]	,015	,000	,04	,14
	4 course	,044	,015	,124	-,01	,09
	5 course	,000	,025	1,000	-,08	,08
	6 course	,397 [*]	,036	,000	,28	,52
3 course	1 course	-,128 [*]	,015	,000	-,18	-,08
	2 course	-,086 [*]	,015	,000	-,14	-,04
	4 course	-,041	,016	,238	-,09	,01
	5 course	-,086 [*]	,025	,037	-,17	,00
	6 course	,311 [*]	,036	,000	,19	,43

4 course	1 course	-,086*	,015	,000	-,14	-,04
	2 course	-,044	,015	,124	-,09	,01
	3 course	,041	,016	,238	-,01	,09
	5 course	-,045	,025	,672	-,13	,04
	6 course	,353*	,037	,000	,23	,47
5 course	1 course	-,042	,024	,707	-,12	,04
	2 course	,000	,025	1,000	-,08	,08
	3 course	,086*	,025	,037	,00	,17
	4 course	,045	,025	,672	-,04	,13
	6 course	,397*	,041	,000	,26	,53
6 course	1 course	-,439*	,036	,000	-,56	-,32
	2 course	-,397*	,036	,000	-,52	-,28
	3 course	-,311*	,036	,000	-,43	-,19
	4 course	-,353*	,037	,000	-,47	-,23
	5 course	-,397*	,041	,000	-,53	-,26

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
0 - 25 proc.	1216	3,27	1,223	,035	3,20	3,34	1	5
26 - 50 proc.	2533	3,55	1,040	,021	3,51	3,59	1	5
51 - 75 proc.	10529	3,74	1,017	,010	3,72	3,75	1	5
76 - 100 proc.	27903	3,96	1,011	,006	3,95	3,97	1	5
Total	42181	3,86	1,033	,005	3,85	3,87	1	5

ANOVA

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1086,302	3	362,101	347,384	,000
Within Groups	43963,810	42177	1,042		
Total	45050,112	42180			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Lectures attendance	(J) Lectures attendance	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0 - 25 proc.	26 - 50 proc.	-,278*	,036	,000	-,38	-,18
	51 - 75 proc.	-,462*	,031	,000	-,55	-,38
	76 - 100 proc.	-,684*	,030	,000	-,77	-,60
26 - 50 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,278*	,036	,000	,18	,38
	51 - 75 proc.	-,184*	,023	,000	-,25	-,12
	76 - 100 proc.	-,406*	,021	,000	-,47	-,35
51 - 75 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,462*	,031	,000	,38	,55
	26 - 50 proc.	,184*	,023	,000	,12	,25
	76 - 100 proc.	-,222*	,012	,000	-,25	-,19
76 - 100 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,684*	,030	,000	,60	,77
	26 - 50 proc.	,406*	,021	,000	,35	,47
	51 - 75 proc.	,222*	,012	,000	,19	,25

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
"Humanitarian Studies"	12058	4,15	,909	,008	4,13	4,17	1	5
"Social Studies"	16546	3,97	,970	,008	3,96	3,99	1	5
"Physical Studies"	7531	3,88	,989	,011	3,85	3,90	1	5
"Biomedical Studies"	6062	3,71	1,073	,014	3,69	3,74	1	5
Total	42197	3,97	,983	,005	3,96	3,98	1	5

ANOVA

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	857,759	3	285,920	302,512	,000
Within Groups	39878,824	42193	,945		
Total	40736,583	42196			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Studies Field Classification	(J) Studies Field Classification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,179 [*]	,012	,000	,15	,21
	"Physical Studies"	,276 [*]	,014	,000	,24	,32
	"Biomedical Studies"	,436 [*]	,015	,000	,39	,48
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,179 [*]	,012	,000	-,21	-,15
	"Physical Studies"	,096 [*]	,014	,000	,06	,13
	"Biomedical Studies"	,257 [*]	,015	,000	,22	,30
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,276 [*]	,014	,000	-,32	-,24
	"Social Studies"	-,096 [*]	,014	,000	-,13	-,06
	"Biomedical Studies"	,161 [*]	,017	,000	,11	,21
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,436 [*]	,015	,000	-,48	-,39
	"Social Studies"	-,257 [*]	,015	,000	-,30	-,22
	"Physical Studies"	-,161 [*]	,017	,000	-,21	-,11

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	27815	3,98	,962	,006	3,97	4,00	1	5
M	5517	4,19	,905	,012	4,16	4,21	1	5
Vn	8712	3,78	1,057	,011	3,76	3,80	1	5
Total	42044	3,97	,982	,005	3,96	3,98	1	5

ANOVA

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	590,466	2	295,233	310,466	,000
Within Groups	39978,272	42041	,951		
Total	40568,737	42043			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies
Scheffe

(I) Level of education	(J) Level of education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,204 [*]	,014	,000	-,24	-,17
	Vn	,207 [*]	,012	,000	,18	,24
M	B	,204 [*]	,014	,000	,17	,24
	Vn	,411 [*]	,017	,000	,37	,45
Vn	B	-,207 [*]	,012	,000	-,24	-,18
	M	-,411 [*]	,017	,000	-,45	-,37

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 course	11900	4,01	,959	,009	4,00	4,03	1	5
2 course	10451	4,02	,972	,010	4,00	4,04	1	5
3 course	8464	3,93	,966	,010	3,91	3,95	1	5
4 course	8376	3,92	1,010	,011	3,90	3,95	1	5
5 course	2125	3,95	1,012	,022	3,90	3,99	1	5
6 course	881	3,61	1,132	,038	3,53	3,68	1	5
Total	42197	3,97	,983	,005	3,96	3,98	1	5

ANOVA

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	191,438	5	38,288	39,842	,000
Within Groups	40545,145	42191	,961		
Total	40736,583	42196			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies
Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 course	2 course	-,005	,013	1,000	-,05	,04
	3 course	,080*	,014	,000	,03	,13
	4 course	,090*	,014	,000	,04	,14
	5 course	,067	,023	,132	-,01	,14
	6 course	,404*	,034	,000	,29	,52
2 course	1 course	,005	,013	1,000	-,04	,05
	3 course	,085*	,014	,000	,04	,13
	4 course	,094*	,014	,000	,05	,14
	5 course	,072	,023	,089	-,01	,15
	6 course	,408*	,034	,000	,29	,52
3 course	1 course	-,080*	,014	,000	-,13	-,03
	2 course	-,085*	,014	,000	-,13	-,04
	4 course	,009	,015	,996	-,04	,06
	5 course	-,013	,024	,998	-,09	,07
	6 course	,323*	,035	,000	,21	,44

4 course	1 course	-,090 [*]	,014	,000	-,14	-,04
	2 course	-,094 [*]	,014	,000	-,14	-,05
	3 course	-,009	,015	,996	-,06	,04
	5 course	-,022	,024	,972	-,10	,06
	6 course	,314 [*]	,035	,000	,20	,43
5 course	1 course	-,067	,023	,132	-,14	,01
	2 course	-,072	,023	,089	-,15	,01
	3 course	,013	,024	,998	-,07	,09
	4 course	,022	,024	,972	-,06	,10
	6 course	,336 [*]	,039	,000	,21	,47
6 course	1 course	-,404 [*]	,034	,000	-,52	-,29
	2 course	-,408 [*]	,034	,000	-,52	-,29
	3 course	-,323 [*]	,035	,000	-,44	-,21
	4 course	-,314 [*]	,035	,000	-,43	-,20
	5 course	-,336 [*]	,039	,000	-,47	-,21

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
0 - 25 proc.	1217	3,41	1,243	,036	3,34	3,48	1	5
26 - 50 proc.	2531	3,70	1,010	,020	3,66	3,74	1	5
51 - 75 proc.	10538	3,88	,956	,009	3,86	3,90	1	5
76 - 100 proc.	27911	4,05	,962	,006	4,04	4,06	1	5
Total	42197	3,97	,983	,005	3,96	3,98	1	5

ANOVA

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	845,546	3	281,849	298,113	,000
Within Groups	39891,037	42193	,945		
Total	40736,583	42196			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.
Scheffe

(I) Lectures attendance	(J) Lectures attendance	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0 - 25 proc.	26 - 50 proc.	-,291 [*]	,034	,000	-,39	-,20
	51 - 75 proc.	-,468 [*]	,029	,000	-,55	-,39
	76 - 100 proc.	-,643 [*]	,028	,000	-,72	-,56
26 - 50 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,291 [*]	,034	,000	,20	,39
	51 - 75 proc.	-,176 [*]	,022	,000	-,24	-,12
	76 - 100 proc.	-,352 [*]	,020	,000	-,41	-,30
51 - 75 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,468 [*]	,029	,000	,39	,55
	26 - 50 proc.	,176 [*]	,022	,000	,12	,24
	76 - 100 proc.	-,175 [*]	,011	,000	-,21	-,14
76 - 100 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,643 [*]	,028	,000	,56	,72
	26 - 50 proc.	,352 [*]	,020	,000	,30	,41
	51 - 75 proc.	,175 [*]	,011	,000	,14	,21

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
"Humanitarian Studies"	12039	3,93	1,037	,009	3,91	3,95	1	5
"Social Studies"	16521	3,74	1,069	,008	3,73	3,76	1	5
"Physical Studies"	7522	3,66	1,047	,012	3,63	3,68	1	5
"Biomedical Studies"	6052	3,44	1,178	,015	3,41	3,47	1	5
Total	42134	3,74	1,084	,005	3,73	3,75	1	5

ANOVA

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1054,828	3	351,609	305,540	,000
Within Groups	48482,267	42130	1,151		
Total	49537,095	42133			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

Scheffe

(I) Studies Field Classification	(J) Studies Field Classification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,190 [*]	,013	,000	,15	,23
	"Physical Studies"	,275 [*]	,016	,000	,23	,32
	"Biomedical Studies"	,496 [*]	,017	,000	,45	,54
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,190 [*]	,013	,000	-,23	-,15
	"Physical Studies"	,085 [*]	,015	,000	,04	,13
	"Biomedical Studies"	,306 [*]	,016	,000	,26	,35
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,275 [*]	,016	,000	-,32	-,23
	"Social Studies"	-,085 [*]	,015	,000	-,13	-,04
	"Biomedical Studies"	,221 [*]	,019	,000	,17	,27
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,496 [*]	,017	,000	-,54	-,45
	"Social Studies"	-,306 [*]	,016	,000	-,35	-,26
	"Physical Studies"	-,221 [*]	,019	,000	-,27	-,17

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	27765	3,76	1,058	,006	3,74	3,77	1	5
M	5511	3,94	1,047	,014	3,91	3,97	1	5
Vn	8705	3,55	1,160	,012	3,53	3,58	1	5
Total	41981	3,74	1,084	,005	3,73	3,75	1	5

ANOVA

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	526,046	2	263,023	226,204	,000
Within Groups	48810,733	41978	1,163		
Total	49336,778	41980			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

Scheffe

(I) Level of education	(J) Level of education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,182 [*]	,016	,000	-,22	-,14
	Vn	,203 [*]	,013	,000	,17	,24
M	B	,182 [*]	,016	,000	,14	,22
	Vn	,385 [*]	,019	,000	,34	,43
Vn	B	-,203 [*]	,013	,000	-,24	-,17
	M	-,385 [*]	,019	,000	-,43	-,34

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 course	11873	3,77	1,064	,010	3,75	3,79	1	5
2 course	10436	3,79	1,073	,011	3,77	3,81	1	5
3 course	8457	3,70	1,072	,012	3,68	3,72	1	5
4 course	8364	3,70	1,110	,012	3,68	3,72	1	5
5 course	2122	3,75	1,124	,024	3,70	3,79	1	5
6 course	882	3,45	1,196	,040	3,37	3,53	1	5
Total	42134	3,74	1,084	,005	3,73	3,75	1	5

ANOVA

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	137,161	5	27,432	23,394	,000
Within Groups	49399,934	42128	1,173		
Total	49537,095	42133			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 course	2 course	-,024	,015	,727	-,07	,02
	3 course	,066 [*]	,015	,002	,02	,12
	4 course	,068 [*]	,015	,002	,02	,12
	5 course	,021	,026	,984	-,06	,11
	6 course	,317 [*]	,038	,000	,19	,44
2 course	1 course	,024	,015	,727	-,02	,07
	3 course	,091 [*]	,016	,000	,04	,14
	4 course	,092 [*]	,016	,000	,04	,15
	5 course	,046	,026	,681	-,04	,13
	6 course	,341 [*]	,038	,000	,21	,47
3 course	1 course	-,066 [*]	,015	,002	-,12	-,02
	2 course	-,091 [*]	,016	,000	-,14	-,04
	4 course	,001	,017	1,000	-,05	,06
	5 course	-,045	,026	,708	-,13	,04
	6 course	,250 [*]	,038	,000	,12	,38

4 course	1 course	-.068 [*]	,015	,002	-,12	-,02
	2 course	-.092 [*]	,016	,000	-,15	-,04
	3 course	-,001	,017	1,000	-,06	,05
	5 course	-,047	,026	,680	-,13	,04
	6 course	,249 [*]	,038	,000	,12	,38
5 course	1 course	-,021	,026	,984	-,11	,06
	2 course	-,046	,026	,681	-,13	,04
	3 course	,045	,026	,708	-,04	,13
	4 course	,047	,026	,680	-,04	,13
	6 course	,295 [*]	,043	,000	,15	,44
6 course	1 course	-,317 [*]	,038	,000	-,44	-,19
	2 course	-,341 [*]	,038	,000	-,47	-,21
	3 course	-,250 [*]	,038	,000	-,38	-,12
	4 course	-,249 [*]	,038	,000	-,38	-,12
	5 course	-,295 [*]	,043	,000	-,44	-,15

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
0 - 25 proc.	1218	3,23	1,234	,035	3,16	3,30	1	5
26 - 50 proc.	2529	3,46	1,072	,021	3,42	3,51	1	5
51 - 75 proc.	10529	3,63	1,057	,010	3,61	3,65	1	5
76 - 100 proc.	27858	3,83	1,075	,006	3,81	3,84	1	5
Total	42134	3,74	1,084	,005	3,73	3,75	1	5

ANOVA

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	848,249	3	282,750	244,661	,000
Within Groups	48688,846	42130	1,156		
Total	49537,095	42133			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking.

Scheffe

(I) Lectures attendance	(J) Lectures attendance	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
0 - 25 proc.	26 - 50 proc.	-,237 [*]	,037	,000	-,34	-,13
	51 - 75 proc.	-,402 [*]	,033	,000	-,49	-,31
	76 - 100 proc.	-,599 [*]	,031	,000	-,69	-,51
26 - 50 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,237 [*]	,037	,000	,13	,34
	51 - 75 proc.	-,166 [*]	,024	,000	-,23	-,10
	76 - 100 proc.	-,362 [*]	,022	,000	-,42	-,30
51 - 75 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,402 [*]	,033	,000	,31	,49
	26 - 50 proc.	,166 [*]	,024	,000	,10	,23
	76 - 100 proc.	-,197 [*]	,012	,000	-,23	-,16
76 - 100 proc.	0 - 25 proc.	,599 [*]	,031	,000	,51	,69
	26 - 50 proc.	,362 [*]	,022	,000	,30	,42
	51 - 75 proc.	,197 [*]	,012	,000	,16	,23

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

- ANOVA tests outputs of interactions between various aspect including in perceived educational service quality –course content quality perception, teaching quality perception, student encouragement to express personal opinion, development of analytical and critical thinking in terms of the different study field, level of education, course and lectures attendance (*Sample 2*)

Descriptives

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Humanitarian studies	2776	3,91	,941	,018	3,87	3,94	1	5
Social studies	3722	3,80	1,005	,016	3,77	3,83	1	5
Physical studies	2168	3,74	,934	,020	3,70	3,78	1	5
Biomedical studies	2212	3,72	,996	,021	3,68	3,76	1	5
Total	10878	3,80	,976	,009	3,78	3,82	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

Scheffe

(I) Field of Science	(J) Field of Science	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Humanitarian studies	Social studies	,110*	,024	,000	,04	,18
	Physical studies	,171*	,028	,000	,09	,25
	Biomedical studies	,192*	,028	,000	,11	,27
Social studies	Humanitarian studies	-,110*	,024	,000	-,18	-,04
	Physical studies	,061	,026	,143	-,01	,13
	Biomedical studies	,082*	,026	,020	,01	,15
Physical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,171*	,028	,000	-,25	-,09
	Social studies	-,061	,026	,143	-,13	,01
	Biomedical studies	,021	,029	,921	-,06	,10
Biomedical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,192*	,028	,000	-,27	-,11
	Social studies	-,082*	,026	,020	-,15	-,01
	Physical studies	-,021	,029	,921	-,10	,06

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	7540	3,80	,965	,011	3,77	3,82	1	5
M	1474	3,75	1,013	,026	3,70	3,80	1	5
Vn	2093	3,86	,996	,022	3,81	3,90	1	5
Total	11107	3,80	,978	,009	3,78	3,82	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.
Scheffe

(I) Level of Education	(J) Level of Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	,049	,028	,206	-,02	,12
	Vn	-,060*	,024	,047	-,12	,00
M	B	-,049	,028	,206	-,12	,02
	Vn	-,109*	,033	,005	-,19	-,03
Vn	B	,060*	,024	,047	,00	,12
	M	,109*	,033	,005	,03	,19

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 kurasas	4185	3,88	,962	,015	3,85	3,91	1	5
2 kurasas	2654	3,77	,965	,019	3,73	3,80	1	5
3 kurasas	2534	3,71	,977	,019	3,68	3,75	1	5
4 kurasas	1250	3,79	1,002	,028	3,73	3,84	1	5
5 kurasas	261	3,52	1,156	,072	3,38	3,66	1	5
6 kurasas	35	3,57	,948	,160	3,25	3,90	1	5
Total	10919	3,79	,979	,009	3,78	3,81	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 1. I am satisfied with quality of courses content.

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 kurasas	2 kurasas	,116*	,024	,000	,04	,20
	3 kurasas	,168*	,025	,000	,09	,25
	4 kurasas	,095	,031	,104	-,01	,20
	5 kurasas	,365*	,062	,000	,16	,57
	6 kurasas	,311	,166	,620	-,24	,86
2 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,116*	,024	,000	-,20	-,04
	3 kurasas	,052	,027	,586	-,04	,14
	4 kurasas	-,021	,033	,996	-,13	,09
	5 kurasas	,249*	,063	,009	,04	,46
	6 kurasas	,195	,166	,927	-,36	,75
3 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,168*	,025	,000	-,25	-,09
	2 kurasas	-,052	,027	,586	-,14	,04
	4 kurasas	-,073	,034	,451	-,19	,04
	5 kurasas	,197	,063	,087	-,01	,41
	6 kurasas	,142	,166	,981	-,41	,70
4 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,095	,031	,104	-,20	,01
	2 kurasas	,021	,033	,996	-,09	,13
	3 kurasas	,073	,034	,451	-,04	,19
	5 kurasas	,270*	,066	,006	,05	,49
	6 kurasas	,216	,167	,893	-,34	,77
5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,365*	,062	,000	-,57	-,16
	2 kurasas	-,249*	,063	,009	-,46	-,04
	3 kurasas	-,197	,063	,087	-,41	,01
	4 kurasas	-,270*	,066	,006	-,49	-,05
	6 kurasas	-,054	,176	1,000	-,64	,53
6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,311	,166	,620	-,86	,24
	2 kurasas	-,195	,166	,927	-,75	,36
	3 kurasas	-,142	,166	,981	-,70	,41
	4 kurasas	-,216	,167	,893	-,77	,34
	5 kurasas	,054	,176	1,000	-,53	,64

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Humanitarian studies	2778	3,85	,967	,018	3,82	3,89	1	5
Social studies	3718	3,78	1,015	,017	3,75	3,81	1	5
Physical studies	2173	3,63	,990	,021	3,59	3,67	1	5
Biomedical studies	2214	3,61	1,036	,022	3,57	3,66	1	5
Total	10883	3,73	1,007	,010	3,72	3,75	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching

Scheffe

(I) Field of Science	(J) Field of Science	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Humanitarian studies	Social studies	,074 [*]	,025	,034	,00	,14
	Physical studies	,224 [*]	,029	,000	,14	,30
	Biomedical studies	,238 [*]	,029	,000	,16	,32
Social studies	Humanitarian studies	-,074 [*]	,025	,034	-,14	,00
	Physical studies	,150 [*]	,027	,000	,07	,23
	Biomedical studies	,164 [*]	,027	,000	,09	,24
Physical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,224 [*]	,029	,000	-,30	-,14
	Social studies	-,150 [*]	,027	,000	-,23	-,07
	Biomedical studies	,015	,030	,971	-,07	,10
Biomedical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,238 [*]	,029	,000	-,32	-,16
	Social studies	-,164 [*]	,027	,000	-,24	-,09
	Physical studies	-,015	,030	,971	-,10	,07

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	7547	3,75	,988	,011	3,73	3,77	1	5
M	1473	3,75	1,037	,027	3,70	3,81	1	5
Vn	2091	3,69	1,066	,023	3,64	3,73	1	5
Total	11111	3,74	1,010	,010	3,72	3,76	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching

Scheffe

(I) Level of Education	(J) Level of Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,006	,029	,978	-,08	,06
	Vn	,061	,025	,052	,00	,12
M	B	,006	,029	,978	-,06	,08
	Vn	,067	,034	,151	-,02	,15
Vn	B	-,061	,025	,052	-,12	,00
	M	-,067	,034	,151	-,15	,02

Descriptives

Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 kursus	4187	3,81	,996	,015	3,78	3,84	1	5
2 kursus	2654	3,69	,999	,019	3,65	3,73	1	5
3 kursus	2537	3,68	1,002	,020	3,64	3,72	1	5
4 kursus	1248	3,73	1,051	,030	3,68	3,79	1	5
5 kursus	261	3,41	1,152	,071	3,27	3,55	1	5
6 kursus	35	3,34	1,027	,174	2,99	3,70	1	5
Total	10922	3,73	1,012	,010	3,71	3,75	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 2. I am satisfied with quality of teaching

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 kurasas	2 kurasas	,124*	,025	,000	,04	,21
	3 kurasas	,137*	,025	,000	,05	,22
	4 kurasas	,079	,033	,314	-,03	,19
	5 kurasas	,404*	,064	,000	,19	,62
	6 kurasas	,471	,171	,181	-,10	1,04
2 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,124*	,025	,000	-,21	-,04
	3 kurasas	,013	,028	,999	-,08	,11
	4 kurasas	-,045	,035	,891	-,16	,07
	5 kurasas	,280*	,065	,003	,06	,50
	6 kurasas	,347	,172	,536	-,22	,92
3 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,137*	,025	,000	-,22	-,05
	2 kurasas	-,013	,028	,999	-,11	,08
	4 kurasas	-,058	,035	,742	-,17	,06
	5 kurasas	,267*	,066	,005	,05	,49
	6 kurasas	,334	,172	,579	-,24	,91
4 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,079	,033	,314	-,19	,03
	2 kurasas	,045	,035	,891	-,07	,16
	3 kurasas	,058	,035	,742	-,06	,17
	5 kurasas	,325*	,069	,000	,10	,55
	6 kurasas	,392	,173	,399	-,18	,97
5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,404*	,064	,000	-,62	-,19
	2 kurasas	-,280*	,065	,003	-,50	-,06
	3 kurasas	-,267*	,066	,005	-,49	-,05
	4 kurasas	-,325*	,069	,000	-,55	-,10
	6 kurasas	,067	,182	1,000	-,54	,67
6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,471	,171	,181	-1,04	,10
	2 kurasas	-,347	,172	,536	-,92	,22
	3 kurasas	-,334	,172	,579	-,91	,24
	4 kurasas	-,392	,173	,399	-,97	,18
	5 kurasas	-,067	,182	1,000	-,67	,54

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Humanitarian studies	2729	4,17	,919	,018	4,13	4,20	1	5
Social studies	3619	3,99	,993	,016	3,96	4,02	1	5
Physical studies	2034	3,60	1,082	,024	3,56	3,65	1	5
Biomedical studies	2161	3,65	1,128	,024	3,60	3,70	1	5
Total	10543	3,89	1,046	,010	3,87	3,91	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Field of Science	(J) Field of Science	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Humanitarian studies	Social studies	,182 [*]	,026	,000	,11	,25
	Physical studies	,565 [*]	,030	,000	,48	,65
	Biomedical studies	,517 [*]	,029	,000	,44	,60
Social studies	Humanitarian studies	-,182 [*]	,026	,000	-,25	-,11
	Physical studies	,383 [*]	,028	,000	,30	,46
	Biomedical studies	,336 [*]	,028	,000	,26	,41
Physical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,565 [*]	,030	,000	-,65	-,48
	Social studies	-,383 [*]	,028	,000	-,46	-,30
	Biomedical studies	-,047	,032	,523	-,14	,04
Biomedical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,517 [*]	,029	,000	-,60	-,44
	Social studies	-,336 [*]	,028	,000	-,41	-,26
	Physical studies	,047	,032	,523	-,04	,14

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	7300	3,88	1,040	,012	3,86	3,90	1	5
M	1417	4,14	,945	,025	4,09	4,19	1	5
Vn	2046	3,77	1,108	,025	3,72	3,82	1	5
Total	10763	3,89	1,047	,010	3,87	3,91	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Level of Education	(J) Level of Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,258 [*]	,030	,000	-,33	-,18
	Vn	,113 [*]	,026	,000	,05	,18
M	B	,258 [*]	,030	,000	,18	,33
	Vn	,371 [*]	,036	,000	,28	,46
Vn	B	-,113 [*]	,026	,000	-,18	-,05
	M	-,371 [*]	,036	,000	-,46	-,28

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 kurasas	4107	3,97	1,023	,016	3,93	4,00	1	5
2 kurasas	2568	3,84	1,070	,021	3,80	3,88	1	5
3 kurasas	2475	3,83	1,028	,021	3,79	3,87	1	5
4 kurasas	1164	3,90	1,093	,032	3,84	3,97	1	5
5 kurasas	248	3,61	1,133	,072	3,47	3,75	1	5
6 kurasas	31	3,84	1,003	,180	3,47	4,21	1	5
Total	10593	3,89	1,049	,010	3,87	3,91	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 kurasas	2 kurasas	,128*	,026	,000	,04	,22
	3 kurasas	,137*	,027	,000	,05	,23
	4 kurasas	,062	,035	,667	-,05	,18
	5 kurasas	,356*	,068	,000	,13	,58
	6 kurasas	,126	,189	,994	-,50	,75
2 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,128*	,026	,000	-,22	-,04
	3 kurasas	,009	,029	1,000	-,09	,11
	4 kurasas	-,066	,037	,670	-,19	,06
	5 kurasas	,228	,070	,057	,00	,46
	6 kurasas	-,002	,189	1,000	-,63	,63
3 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,137*	,027	,000	-,23	-,05
	2 kurasas	-,009	,029	1,000	-,11	,09
	4 kurasas	-,075	,037	,545	-,20	,05
	5 kurasas	,219	,070	,078	-,01	,45
	6 kurasas	-,010	,189	1,000	-,64	,62
4 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,062	,035	,667	-,18	,05
	2 kurasas	,066	,037	,670	-,06	,19
	3 kurasas	,075	,037	,545	-,05	,20
	5 kurasas	,294*	,073	,006	,05	,54
	6 kurasas	,064	,190	1,000	-,57	,70
5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,356*	,068	,000	-,58	-,13
	2 kurasas	-,228	,070	,057	-,46	,00
	3 kurasas	-,219	,070	,078	-,45	,01
	4 kurasas	-,294*	,073	,006	-,54	-,05
	6 kurasas	-,230	,199	,932	-,89	,43
6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,126	,189	,994	-,75	,50
	2 kurasas	,002	,189	1,000	-,63	,63
	3 kurasas	,010	,189	1,000	-,62	,64
	4 kurasas	-,064	,190	1,000	-,70	,57
	5 kurasas	,230	,199	,932	-,43	,89

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Humanitarian studies	2732	4,18	,909	,017	4,14	4,21	1	5
Social studies	3634	4,02	,976	,016	3,99	4,06	1	5
Physical studies	2060	3,88	1,004	,022	3,83	3,92	1	5
Biomedical studies	2163	3,82	1,083	,023	3,77	3,86	1	5
Total	10589	3,99	,997	,010	3,97	4,01	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.
Scheffe

(I) Field of Science	(J) Field of Science	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Humanitarian studies	Social studies	,155 [*]	,025	,000	,08	,22
	Physical studies	,302 [*]	,029	,000	,22	,38
	Biomedical studies	,364 [*]	,028	,000	,28	,44
Social studies	Humanitarian studies	-,155 [*]	,025	,000	-,22	-,08
	Physical studies	,148 [*]	,027	,000	,07	,22
	Biomedical studies	,209 [*]	,027	,000	,13	,28
Physical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,302 [*]	,029	,000	-,38	-,22
	Social studies	-,148 [*]	,027	,000	-,22	-,07
	Biomedical studies	,061	,030	,257	-,02	,15
Biomedical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,364 [*]	,028	,000	-,44	-,28
	Social studies	-,209 [*]	,027	,000	-,28	-,13
	Physical studies	-,061	,030	,257	-,15	,02

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	7341	3,99	,981	,011	3,97	4,02	1	5
M	1420	4,21	,915	,024	4,16	4,25	1	5
Vn	2049	3,84	1,083	,024	3,79	3,89	1	5
Total	10810	3,99	,998	,010	3,97	4,01	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.
Scheffe

(I) Level of Education	(J) Level of Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,213*	,029	,000	-,28	-,14
	Vn	,153*	,025	,000	,09	,21
M	B	,213*	,029	,000	,14	,28
	Vn	,366*	,034	,000	,28	,45
Vn	B	-,153*	,025	,000	-,21	-,09
	M	-,366*	,034	,000	-,45	-,28

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 kurasas	4109	4,01	,998	,016	3,98	4,04	1	5
2 kurasas	2579	3,98	,997	,020	3,94	4,02	1	5
3 kurasas	2486	3,96	,960	,019	3,92	4,00	1	5
4 kurasas	1185	4,03	1,037	,030	3,98	4,09	1	5
5 kurasas	249	3,68	1,175	,074	3,53	3,83	1	5
6 kurasas	32	3,94	1,014	,179	3,57	4,30	1	5
Total	10640	3,99	,999	,010	3,97	4,01	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during th
Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I- J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 kurasas	2 kurasas	,032	,025	,898	-,05	,12
	3 kurasas	,050	,025	,566	-,03	,13
	4 kurasas	-,022	,033	,993	-,13	,09
	5 kurasas	,333*	,065	,000	,12	,55
	6 kurasas	,075	,177	,999	-,51	,66
2 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,032	,025	,898	-,12	,05
	3 kurasas	,018	,028	,995	-,08	,11
	4 kurasas	-,054	,035	,790	-,17	,06
	5 kurasas	,302*	,066	,001	,08	,52
	6 kurasas	,043	,178	1,000	-,55	,63
3 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,050	,025	,566	-,13	,03
	2 kurasas	-,018	,028	,995	-,11	,08
	4 kurasas	-,072	,035	,518	-,19	,04
	5 kurasas	,283*	,066	,003	,06	,50
	6 kurasas	,025	,178	1,000	-,57	,62
4 kurasas	1 kurasas	,022	,033	,993	-,09	,13
	2 kurasas	,054	,035	,790	-,06	,17
	3 kurasas	,072	,035	,518	-,04	,19
	5 kurasas	,356*	,070	,000	,12	,59
	6 kurasas	,097	,179	,998	-,50	,69
5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,333*	,065	,000	-,55	-,12
	2 kurasas	-,302*	,066	,001	-,52	-,08
	3 kurasas	-,283*	,066	,003	-,50	-,06
	4 kurasas	-,356*	,070	,000	-,59	-,12
	6 kurasas	-,259	,187	,862	-,88	,36
6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,075	,177	,999	-,66	,51
	2 kurasas	-,043	,178	1,000	-,63	,55
	3 kurasas	-,025	,178	1,000	-,62	,57
	4 kurasas	-,097	,179	,998	-,69	,50
	5 kurasas	,259	,187	,862	-,36	,88

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Humanitarian studies	2716	4,02	,998	,019	3,99	4,06	1	5
Social studies	3606	3,87	1,054	,018	3,84	3,91	1	5
Physical studies	2051	3,75	1,074	,024	3,71	3,80	1	5
Biomedical studies	2130	3,58	1,175	,025	3,53	3,63	1	5
Total	10503	3,83	1,081	,011	3,81	3,85	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking

Scheffe

(I) Field of Science	(J) Field of Science	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Humanitarian studies	Social studies	,150 [*]	,027	,000	,07	,23
	Physical studies	,272 [*]	,031	,000	,18	,36
	Biomedical studies	,447 [*]	,031	,000	,36	,53
Social studies	Humanitarian studies	-,150 [*]	,027	,000	-,23	-,07
	Physical studies	,122 [*]	,030	,001	,04	,20
	Biomedical studies	,297 [*]	,029	,000	,22	,38
Physical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,272 [*]	,031	,000	-,36	-,18
	Social studies	-,122 [*]	,030	,001	-,20	-,04
	Biomedical studies	,175 [*]	,033	,000	,08	,27
Biomedical studies	Humanitarian studies	-,447 [*]	,031	,000	-,53	-,36
	Social studies	-,297 [*]	,029	,000	-,38	-,22
	Physical studies	-,175 [*]	,033	,000	-,27	-,08

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
B	7272	3,84	1,061	,012	3,81	3,86	1	5
M	1413	4,01	1,036	,028	3,95	4,06	1	5
Vn	2038	3,68	1,159	,026	3,63	3,73	1	5
Total	10723	3,83	1,081	,010	3,81	3,85	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking

Scheffe

(I) Level of Education	(J) Level of Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
B	M	-,172 [*]	,031	,000	-,25	-,09
	Vn	,154 [*]	,027	,000	,09	,22
M	B	,172 [*]	,031	,000	,09	,25
	Vn	,325 [*]	,037	,000	,23	,42
Vn	B	-,154 [*]	,027	,000	-,22	-,09
	M	-,325 [*]	,037	,000	-,42	-,23

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptives

Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 kursus	4081	3,87	1,067	,017	3,84	3,90	1	5
2 kursus	2563	3,83	1,082	,021	3,78	3,87	1	5
3 kursus	2466	3,76	1,080	,022	3,72	3,80	1	5
4 kursus	1167	3,87	1,096	,032	3,80	3,93	1	5
5 kursus	247	3,51	1,196	,076	3,36	3,66	1	5
6 kursus	33	3,82	1,103	,192	3,43	4,21	1	5
Total	10557	3,82	1,082	,011	3,80	3,85	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 kurasas	2 kurasas	,046	,027	,722	-,04	,14
	3 kurasas	,112*	,028	,005	,02	,20
	4 kurasas	,006	,036	1,000	-,11	,13
	5 kurasas	,366*	,071	,000	,13	,60
	6 kurasas	,053	,189	1,000	-,57	,68
2 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,046	,027	,722	-,14	,04
	3 kurasas	,066	,030	,446	-,03	,17
	4 kurasas	-,040	,038	,955	-,17	,09
	5 kurasas	,320*	,072	,001	,08	,56
	6 kurasas	,007	,189	1,000	-,62	,64
3 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,112*	,028	,005	-,20	-,02
	2 kurasas	-,066	,030	,446	-,17	,03
	4 kurasas	-,106	,038	,175	-,23	,02
	5 kurasas	,253*	,072	,031	,01	,49
	6 kurasas	-,059	,189	1,000	-,69	,57
4 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,006	,036	1,000	-,13	,11
	2 kurasas	,040	,038	,955	-,09	,17
	3 kurasas	,106	,038	,175	-,02	,23
	5 kurasas	,359*	,076	,000	,11	,61
	6 kurasas	,047	,191	1,000	-,59	,68
5 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,366*	,071	,000	-,60	-,13
	2 kurasas	-,320*	,072	,001	-,56	-,08
	3 kurasas	-,253*	,072	,031	-,49	-,01
	4 kurasas	-,359*	,076	,000	-,61	-,11
	6 kurasas	-,312	,200	,787	-,98	,35
6 kurasas	1 kurasas	-,053	,189	1,000	-,68	,57
	2 kurasas	-,007	,189	1,000	-,64	,62
	3 kurasas	,059	,189	1,000	-,57	,69
	4 kurasas	-,047	,191	1,000	-,68	,59
	5 kurasas	,312	,200	,787	-,35	,98

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.2. Differences in students satisfaction and loyalty intentions in different study field, level of education and course (MANOVA analysis)

Between-Subjects Factors

		Value Label	N
Field of Science	1,00	Humanitarian studies	2657
	2,00	Social studies	3571
	3,00	Physical studies	2066
	4,00	Biomedical studies	2115

Between-Subjects Factors

		Value Label	N
Level of Education	1	B	7204
	2	M	1423
	3	Vn	2000

Between-Subjects Factors

		Value Label	N
Study Course	1,00	1 kurasas	4007
	2,00	2 kurasas	2557
	3,00	3 kurasas	2411
	4,00	4 kurasas	1186
	5,00	5 kurasas	244
	6,00	6 kurasas	34

Descriptives

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
"Humanitarian Studies"	12071	3,95	1,061	,010	3,93	3,96	1	5
"Social Studies"	16566	3,83	1,062	,008	3,82	3,85	1	5
"Physical Studies"	7560	3,74	1,066	,012	3,71	3,76	1	5
"Biomedical Studies"	6073	3,69	1,122	,014	3,66	3,72	1	5
Total	42270	3,83	1,075	,005	3,82	3,84	1	5

ANOVA

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	351,809	3	117,270	102,176	,000
Within Groups	48509,522	42266	1,148		
Total	48861,331	42269			

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Scheffe

(I) Studies Field Classification	(J) Studies Field Classification	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
"Humanitarian Studies"	"Social Studies"	,111 [*]	,013	,000	,08	,15
	"Physical Studies"	,210 [*]	,016	,000	,17	,25
	"Biomedical Studies"	,258 [*]	,017	,000	,21	,31
"Social Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,111 [*]	,013	,000	-,15	-,08
	"Physical Studies"	,099 [*]	,015	,000	,06	,14
	"Biomedical Studies"	,147 [*]	,016	,000	,10	,19
"Physical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,210 [*]	,016	,000	-,25	-,17
	"Social Studies"	-,099 [*]	,015	,000	-,14	-,06
	"Biomedical Studies"	,048	,018	,079	,00	,10
"Biomedical Studies"	"Humanitarian Studies"	-,258 [*]	,017	,000	-,31	-,21
	"Social Studies"	-,147 [*]	,016	,000	-,19	-,10
	"Physical Studies"	-,048	,018	,079	-,10	,00

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

ANOVA

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1419,953	5	283,991	252,998	,000
Within Groups	47441,378	42264	1,123		
Total	48861,331	42269			

Descriptives

Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
1 course	11920	4,07	,980	,009	4,05	4,09	1	5
2 course	10476	3,84	1,057	,010	3,82	3,86	1	5
3 course	8474	3,70	1,077	,012	3,68	3,72	1	5
4 course	8393	3,69	1,117	,012	3,66	3,71	1	5
5 course	2125	3,73	1,100	,024	3,69	3,78	1	5
6 course	882	3,16	1,270	,043	3,08	3,25	1	5
Total	42270	3,83	1,075	,005	3,82	3,84	1	5

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Scheffe

(I) Study Course	(J) Study Course	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 course	2 course	,230*	,014	,000	,18	,28
	3 course	,370*	,015	,000	,32	,42
	4 course	,385*	,015	,000	,34	,44
	5 course	,337*	,025	,000	,25	,42
	6 course	,906*	,037	,000	,78	1,03
2 course	1 course	-,230*	,014	,000	-,28	-,18
	3 course	,140*	,015	,000	,09	,19
	4 course	,156*	,016	,000	,10	,21
	5 course	,107*	,025	,003	,02	,19
	6 course	,677*	,037	,000	,55	,80
3 course	1 course	-,370*	,015	,000	-,42	-,32
	2 course	-,140*	,015	,000	-,19	-,09
	4 course	,015	,016	,972	-,04	,07
	5 course	-,033	,026	,891	-,12	,05
	6 course	,536*	,037	,000	,41	,66
4 course	1 course	-,385*	,015	,000	-,44	-,34
	2 course	-,156*	,016	,000	-,21	-,10
	3 course	-,015	,016	,972	-,07	,04
	5 course	-,049	,026	,612	-,13	,04
	6 course	,521*	,038	,000	,40	,65
5 course	1 course	-,337*	,025	,000	-,42	-,25
	2 course	-,107*	,025	,003	-,19	-,02
	3 course	,033	,026	,891	-,05	,12
	4 course	,049	,026	,612	-,04	,13
	6 course	,570*	,042	,000	,43	,71
6 course	1 course	-,906*	,037	,000	-1,03	-,78
	2 course	-,677*	,037	,000	-,80	-,55
	3 course	-,536*	,037	,000	-,66	-,41
	4 course	-,521*	,038	,000	-,65	-,40
	5 course	-,570*	,042	,000	-,71	-,43

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.3. Relationship between perceived educational service quality as well as overall satisfaction and loyalty intentions in higher education sector

Linear regression between overall satisfaction and loyalty

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,395	,036		10,904	,000
	Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.	,878	,009	,699	100,652	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,699 ^a	,488	,488	,873	1,967

a. Predictors: (Constant), Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

b. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7720,012	1	7720,012	10130,920	,000 ^b
	Residual	8096,513	10625	,762		
	Total	15816,525	10626			

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

b. Predictors: (Constant), Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.

Mediation.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,095	,039		2,427	,015		
	Item 3. Students were encouraged to express their opinion during the studies.	,187	,010	,160	19,640	,000	,716	1,396
	Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.	,772	,010	,615	75,304	,000	,716	1,396

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,032	,040		,792	,428		
	Item 4. Students were encouraged to analyze and solve various problems by oneself during the studies.	,203	,010	,166	20,507	,000	,732	1,366
	Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.	,768	,010	,612	75,733	,000	,732	1,366

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	,087	,038		2,284	,022		
	Item 5. Course content develops students' skills of critical thinking	,221	,009	,195	23,850	,000	,705	1,418
	Item 6. I am satisfied with my studies overall.	,744	,010	,592	72,331	,000	,705	1,418

a. Dependent Variable: Item 7. If I have to choose my studies again, I would study at the same university.

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